

Grant agreement no. 312788

**ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK**

<http://odin-project.eu>

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3 – Proofs of concept

**V1_0
Final**

Abstract: The proofs of concept in HSS and HEP have shown how the shared foundations in their ultimate aims, data sharing and author recognition, lead to a convergent evolution. The results obtained served to consolidate a generic workflow for the integration of persistent identifiers and its consequent application in different case studies. This document describes the shared workflows, their application and the remaining challenges for both disciplines.

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	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final

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Introduction

1. WORK PACKAGE OVERVIEW

In the first year of ODIN, this work package examined challenges in data discovery and interoperability, and the current state of persistent identifier adoption for data and contributors. The work focused on the High-Energy Physics (HEP) and the Humanities and Social Science (HSS) communities and produced two proofs of concept [deliverable 3.1 “Humanities and Social Science Proof of Concept” [2] and deliverable 3.2 “Proof of Concept HEP” [3]], which outlined the two disciplinary examples and identified issues across the communities to set the stage for the final WP3 deliverable.

In the second project year, the proof of concept analysis included new case studies, the UK Archaeology Data Service (ADS)¹, and the MRC National Survey of Health and Development (MRC NSHD)² in the UK, where their work was used to implement DOIs and author IDs to test the proof of concept. The analysis was extended with a multiple point comparison of the HSS and HEP examples to improve understanding of current practice and establish a broad view of the community needs. Requirements for workflows to integrate persistent identifiers for persons and research objects were described and built upon this analysis. From that, value added services and tools were developed, as were integrations with the ORCID and DataCite persistent identifier platforms. This work is presented in the service provision chapter, along with a detailed overview of the technical infrastructure and internal processes used in the case studies of INSPIRE, ADS and MRC NSHD. The practical, cultural or other differences (e.g. in terms of metadata) between the HSS and HEP data management processes and the remaining gaps or challenges that need to be addressed have been described as well.

This report thus addresses the final part of the objective for Work Package 3, defined in the project’s Description of Work (DoW), as “identify, by a critical analysis of the proofs of concept, common issues in open and interoperable permanent identifiers of data and contributors, by establishing a common cross-disciplinary view on the relevant workflows”.

¹ Archaeology Data Service: <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

² LHA National Survey of Health and Development: <http://www.nshd.mrc.ac.uk/>

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1.1. Proofs of concept and commonalities

The proofs of concept were based on two case studies carried out in two widely divergent disciplinary areas: Humanities and Social Sciences and High Energy Physics. The goal was to understand current practices and determine commonalities in dataset schemas and data citation between these fields, with the assumption that a stronger case for a common approach to a persistent identifier based research data e-infrastructure could be built from these points of convergence.

The HSS proof of concept investigated the present status of the adoption of description schemas for datasets and of data citation practices with a particular focus on the adoption and interoperability of persistent identifiers. The British birth cohort studies³ available from the UK Data Service served as the centre of the HSS case study. A variety of workflows were analysed in relation to data citation, as well as the UK Data Archive's⁴ OAIS⁵-based preliminary workflows for assigning persistent identifiers.

The HEP case study focused on the digital library INSPIRE, an information hub that serves the entire HEP field. Preliminary workflows and models for data exchange were analysed across many systems and determined specific e-infrastructure needs.

The final step was a detailed comparison between HSS and HEP use cases to pinpoint similarities and opportunities for a shared approach.

³ Longitudinal studies funded by the UK's Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) and Medical Research Council (MRC) and archived at the UK Data Archive (UKDA). For example, those at the Centre for Longitudinal Studies, <http://www.cls.ioe.ac.uk/>

⁴ The UK Data Archive manages the UK Data Service. The service is how users interact with the UK Data Archive. This paper refers to the UKDA throughout, unless talking specifically about the Service.

⁵ Open Archival Information System, ISO 14721:2012: http://www.iso.org/iso/catalogue_detail.htm?csnumber=57284

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1.2. Multidisciplinary service provision support

HSS integrates multiples disciplines, with a diversity of needs, whereas in HEP, INSPIRE centralises available resources. Looking beyond the proofs of concept, ODIN has supported two particular case studies in HSS, ADS and MRC NSHD, as well as the technical development of INSPIRE as a hub for its community.

The application of the common workflows showed how each case study required different approaches, and served to validate the results obtained and to clarify the remaining challenges.

Proofs of concept: Comparative analysis, commonalities and differences

2. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PROOF OF CONCEPT WORKFLOWS

To gain a better understanding of the process used to manage research data in each discipline a comparative analysis took place, paying particular attention to data submission workflows and assignment and integration of persistent identifiers. To facilitate comparison, the data submission process workflows of the UKDA and INSPIRE were charted (Figures 1-4).

Figure 1. UKDA workflow for new data

Figure 2. UKDA workflow for current data

Figures 1 and 2 show the UKDA workflows for assigning identifiers to newly ingested data and for the retrospective assignment of identifiers to previously ingested data. In the same manner, Figures 3 and 4 show the same two workflows for INSPIRE. Both the UKDA and INSPIRE have simple data acquisition mechanisms in place and use OAIS procedures: the data travels from the data producer to the final consumer and undergoes management, or in OAIS terms, the data begins at the Submission Information Package (SIP) stage, moves to ingest and then data management or archival storage (namely the Archival Information Package, AIP, stage), and culminates in the Dissemination Information Package (DIP) stage, wherein the user (consumer) is able to access the data.

Figure 3. INSPIRE workflow for new data

Figure 4. INSPIRE workflow for current data

To establish a cross-disciplinary view on the relevant workflows, points of commonality across the two proofs of concept workflows were compiled into a single generic workflow, which is discussed in the next section.

2.1. From the proofs of concept to a generic workflow for data management

Using the OAIS model as a common reference, a generic workflow was drawn up, to highlight the intervention points for ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Generic workflow based on the proofs of concept and their OAIS background

The ease of developing a generic workflow from the two proofs of concept in very disparate disciplines suggests there are underlying commonalities in the data systems that have contributed to a common way of working. It was unclear initially, whether this commonality was driven by OAIS compliance, or something more profound. This was investigated in year 2.

A number of cultural commonalities between the two proofs of concept may have contributed to workflow commonalities. Both proofs of concept:

- are from subject-specific data repositories;
- receive data that is generated independently from the archive;
- receive data as defined, fixed objects;
- give all data that is accepted into the archive a DOI;
- have chosen to use DataCite DOIs;

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- are coordinated with international efforts⁶; and,
- were established before the use of DOIs for data and name identifiers were widely adopted and have chosen to assign DataCite DOIs to all data that is accepted into the archive

However, practice may differ between these proofs of concept and repositories that:

- cover a broad range of subjects;
- only hold in-house generated data;
- receive data that changes over time;
- use identifiers other than DOIs; and,
- receive data that they do not want to assign a DOI to (at least initially).

Such differences may result in distinct approaches between the proofs of concept and repositories in the wider research landscape. So, to draw out commonalities that hold across the wider research landscape, the common workflow approach was further validated, by:

- implementing the generic workflow with a second, distinct social science data repository (MRC National Survey of Health and Development, NSHD);
- implementing workflow updates to INSPIRE;
- carrying out a case study in a humanities data centre (Archaeological Data Service, ADS, in the UK); and,
- inviting comment from GESIS⁷, a national social science data centre in Germany.

These validations not only highlighted commonalities in the workflow across a wider range of repositories, but also highlighted areas of difference that provided an opportunity to improve the generic workflow and accommodate a wider suite of use cases. These findings and the updated generic workflow are presented in Chapter 3.

⁶ While INSPIRE-HEP is itself the international partnership within its field, the UKDA is part of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) <http://www.cessda.net/>

⁷ <http://www.gesis.org/en/home/>

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2.2. Workflow phases in detail

Presented below are the core steps within the generic workflow developed from the proofs of concept and validated by further case studies and implementation of the workflow.

2.2.1. Data Deposit

While data management after submission follows a standard path, UKDA and INSPIRE receive data in different ways. This results in variations in the metadata available at deposit.

Data and metadata are deposited manually to the UKDA by the data creators. The deposit form⁸ requests a wide range of metadata from the submitter, including:

- bibliographic (creators, depositors, contributors and funders; abstract; subjects; versioning; temporal and geographic coverage);
- technical (data file formats; digitisation details); and,
- subject-specific (anonymisation; documentation; methodology)

The deposit form, shown in Figure 6, is then submitted alongside data files. This is then manually input into the UKDA by curators.

To reduce the burden on archive staff and the lead time to implementation, the UKDA would prefer ORCID iDs or other name and organizational identifiers to be included in the submission metadata. However, the procedure is already in place with other data archives, such as the ADS, which already requests ORCID iDs on submission.

In many cases, the UKDA receives data from projects funded by the UK Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), as data deposit is mandated by them. But they do not receive details about these projects from funders alongside deposited metadata. Some

⁸ <http://ukdataservice.ac.uk/deposit-data/how-to/regular/regular-depositors.aspx>

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institutional repositories⁹ are looking at how their data management system or repository integrates with their current research information system (CRIS)¹⁰. The CRIS maintains records about their researchers, funding and outputs, and there is, therefore a clear advantage to ensuring these records and data repository records are linked through the use of persistent identifiers and eliminating the need for re-entry of information.

UK Data Service - Data deposit form

A full description of your data collection will be included in its online data catalogue record. This description will be based largely upon the information provided by you in this form. Please try to complete as much of the form as possible. If you need assistance, email collections@ukdataservice.ac.uk.

1. Study description

Title

This should reflect the nature and subject of the data collection and include a date e.g. General Household Survey, 2001-2002. We may amend the title to reflect current cataloguing standards.

[Click here to enter text.](#)

Abstract

The general aims, purpose and background to the data collection (300 words max).

[Click here to enter text.](#)

Main topics

Provide information about the main subject coverage of the data e.g. the public's perception of their neighbourhoods and fear of crime; workplace relations and employment practices.

[Click here to enter text.](#)

Edition/version

Is this a new edition, extract or version of the data collection?

Yes, please provide details. [Click here to enter text.](#)

No

Related data

If the data collection is derived from or is closely related to others, list details. If any of these data collections are available from the UK Data Service, please indicate the study number(s).

[Click here to enter text.](#)

URL

Website address containing information relevant for the data collection:

[Click here to enter text.](#)

Subject categories (select up to six)

<p>Economics</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Consumer behaviour <input type="checkbox"/> Economic conditions and indicators <input type="checkbox"/> Economic systems and development <input type="checkbox"/> Income, property and investment	<p>Industry and management</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture, forestry and rural industry <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial/commercial location <input type="checkbox"/> Management and organisation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade, industry and markets
<p>Education</p> <input type="checkbox"/> General <input type="checkbox"/> Higher and further <input type="checkbox"/> Literacy <input type="checkbox"/> Primary, pre-primary and secondary <input type="checkbox"/> Research <input type="checkbox"/> School leaving <input type="checkbox"/> Teaching profession	<p>Law, crime and legal systems</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Crime and law enforcement <input type="checkbox"/> Legislation and legal systems
<p>Employment and labour</p> <input type="checkbox"/> General <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial relations <input type="checkbox"/> Retirement <input type="checkbox"/> Training <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployment	<p>Media, communication and language</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Information technology <input type="checkbox"/> Language and linguistics <input type="checkbox"/> Mass media
<p>Environment, conservation and land use</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Energy and fuel <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental and conservation issues <input type="checkbox"/> Land use and planning <input type="checkbox"/> Natural landscapes <input type="checkbox"/> New town studies <input type="checkbox"/> Plant and animal distribution	<p>Politics</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Conflict, security and peace <input type="checkbox"/> Election and campaign studies <input type="checkbox"/> Election returns <input type="checkbox"/> Government and political systems <input type="checkbox"/> International politics and organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Political behaviour and attitudes
<p>Health</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Accidents and injuries <input type="checkbox"/> Childbearing, family planning and abortion <input type="checkbox"/> Drug abuse, alcohol and smoking <input type="checkbox"/> General <input type="checkbox"/> Health services and medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Mental health	<p>Population, vital statistics and censuses</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Migration <input type="checkbox"/> Morbidity and mortality <input type="checkbox"/> Population censuses <input type="checkbox"/> Population studies <input type="checkbox"/> Vital statistics
	<p>Psychology</p> <p>Reference and instructional resources</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Computer and simulation programs <input type="checkbox"/> Reference sources <input type="checkbox"/> Teaching packages and test datasets <input type="checkbox"/> Regular opinion polls

Figure 6. The first two pages of the 9-page deposit form for regular contributors of longitudinal data to the UKDA

Conversely, while INSPIRE does receive a small number of direct data submissions, the majority of its data and metadata is harvested from third parties, where differing

⁹ Some relevant case studies include PURE integration with Equella at the Royal Holloway University of London (http://www.equella.com/media/26847/equella_rhul_case_study.pdf). Pure also integrates with DSpace and Eprints, but it can also replace the institutional repository itself, such as at Aalborg University (<http://vbn.aau.dk/en/>). See more details: <http://research-data-toolkit.herts.ac.uk/2012/05/atira-pure-cris-roundup/>

¹⁰ http://www.eurocris.org/Index.php?page=concepts_benefits&t=1

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metadata schemas are used. INSPIRE harmonises the process by mapping them to its own internal schema, based on the MARC21 standard. In most cases, name or organizational identifiers tend to be present as part of the harvested metadata, as they are as useful to the third party repository.

2.2.2. Ingest

In both the HSS and HEP proofs of concept, the DOI minting step occurs during ingest. This timing was validated by both the ADS and GESIS case studies.

In the HSS proof of concept, data goes through a quality assurance step during the ingest process. At this point, data may be rejected from inclusion into the repository, which means assignment of an object identifier is not guaranteed. Where datasets are ingested, the metadata required to mint a DOI is typically available. In addition, a DOI is a required component of the metadata required for archiving and dissemination, further validating the timing of DOI assignment.

INSPIRE does not undertake a detailed quality assurance process over the data and metadata ingested, assuming this will have already occurred at the third party repository. However, on harvesting, metadata is checked via a dedicated module and if issues are detected, metadata is improved before the ingest process continues.

The ingest process also includes a point where creators and contributors can be verified. Both UKDA and INSPIRE maintain a table or database that serves as an authority file for creators and contributors, that is updated or cross-referenced during the ingest process. Figure 7 shows where currently¹¹ names from the name authority file can be added to datasets during the curation process.

¹¹ The UKDA are updating their systems before the end of 2014

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Input Programs
LOGIN/REGISTER

HOME FINDING ORDERING USING CREATING DEPOSITING

Finding Data Browse by Subject **Input Programs** Study Status Other Data Sources

Please Enter Title/SN

Status: **Republishing By :**

<input type="checkbox"/>	SN Number: 7500	<input type="button" value="Edit"/>	<input type="button" value="Publish"/>
	Title: British Social Attitudes Survey, 2013 Sub Title: Alternative Title: BSA Series Title : Project Number : Data Type : UK Survey data		
	Index Keywords: <input type="button" value="Index Keywords"/> <input type="button" value="List Keywords"/>		
	Distribution: <i>Distributor:</i> ESDS Government <i>Availability:</i> UK Data Service <i>Contact:</i> Get in touch <i>Date of Deposit:</i> 21 May 2014 <i>Date of Distribution:</i> 27 July 2014		
	Subject Category: Higher and further - Education Environmental and conservation issues - Environment, conservation and land use General - Health Gender roles - Social stratification and groupings General - Social welfare policy and systems		
	Depositor: <input type="button" value="Add Depositor"/> <input type="button" value="Delete Depositor"/> NatCen Social Research		
	Principal Investigator: <input type="button" value="Add Principal Investigator"/> <input type="button" value="Delete Principal Investigator"/> NatCen Social Research		
	Data Collector: <input type="button" value="Add Data Collector"/>		
	Original Producer: <input type="button" value="Add Original Producer"/>		
	Sponsor: <input type="button" value="Add Sponsor"/> <input type="button" value="Delete Sponsor"/>		

Figure 7. A UKDA curator's view of a longitudinal study data record, with sections for adding selections from the name authority files

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The ingestion of data is the step that includes association of an object DOI within the HSS proof of concept and further case studies. At the UKDA, the data undergoes expert quality checks before it is accepted and assigned a DataCite DOI. Figure 8 is a screen capture of the administrative end of the UKDA's ReShare repository¹², showing when data can be approved (icon with a green tick) and a DOI assigned. Figure 9 shows the current UKDA curator's interface with a button to assign a DOI.

UK Data Service ReShare

Home Legal Review procedures

Review

Help

Filter

Displaying results 1 to 10 of 69. Show 10, 25 or 100 results per page.
1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | Next

Data collection ID	Item type	Last status change	Depositing user	Grant reference	Type of data	
850784	Data Collection	11 Jul 2014 12:21	Rachael Kotarski	EP/L015123/1	Qualitative and mixed methods data	
850859	Data Collection	29 Apr 2014 16:19	Rachael Kotarski	EP/L015123/1	Qualitative and mixed methods data	
851030	Data Collection	29 Apr 2014 15:48	Rachael Kotarski	EP/L015123/1	Experimental data	
851057	Data Collection	29 Apr 2014 13:27	Rachael Kotarski	EP/L015123/1	Qualitative and mixed methods data, UK survey data	
851258	Data Collection	20 Jun 2014 09:44	Patricia Herterich	EP/L015123/1	Other surveys	

Figure 8. Curator's view of data submitted to the UKDA's ReShare repository

¹² The ReShare repository is a new part of the UK Data Service, run from the UK Data Archive. It does not manage the longitudinal data examined for the Proof of Concept, but does provide similar functionality, so it is shown here for demonstration purposes. More detail on the ReShare repository can be found at <http://reshare.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

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The longitudinal data held by UKDA is represented by 'waves' of data collection. Each wave is assigned its own DOI on ingest. To aid user navigation of longitudinal datasets, the DOIs for different waves of the same study are linked to the same landing page.

UK Data Archive
www.data-archive.ac.uk

Input Programs

LOGIN/REGISTER | YOUR ORDER

HOME FINDING ORDERING USING CREATING DEPOSITING

Finding Data Browse by Subject **Input Programs** Study Status Other Data Sources

SN 7500 - British Social Attitudes Survey, 2013

* Internal User * External View

[Online Documentation](#)

Assigned Keyword List for SN:7500

EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

Search on Keyword Browse Thesaurus release datasets

release datasets and mint DOI Input Programs

Title:
British Social Attitudes Survey, 2013
(BSA)

Subject Categories:
British Social Attitudes Survey - Major studies
Higher and further - Education
Social attitudes and behaviour - Society and culture
Environmental and conservation issues - Environment, conservation and land use
Social indicators and quality of life - Society and culture
General - Health
Gender roles - Social stratification and groupings
General - Social welfare policy and systems

Figure 9. A UKDA curator's view of a dataset, showing the 'release datasets and mint DOI' button

Figure 10 shows the landing page for the DOIs of different waves of the Quarterly Labour Force Survey [6].

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[Contact UK Data Service](#)

UK Data Service

A new Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is assigned to the data collection each time there is a major change to data, documentation or metadata. The new DOI will resolve to an updated version of this page containing a log of changes to this data collection since the allocation of its first DOI. The DOI system supports resource discovery and simplifies citation for users of data collections. Data producers benefit directly through increased visibility of their work.

10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-3	Full catalogue record >
<p>Citation: Office for National Statistics. Social Survey Division and Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency. Central Survey Unit, <i>Quarterly Labour Force Survey, January - March, 2011: Special Licence Access</i> [computer file]. 3rd Edition. Colchester, Essex: UK Data Archive [distributor], January 2014. SN: 6903, http://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-3</p> <p>Change log: 14 January 2014: For the third edition (January 2014) a new version of the data file was deposited, including variables Caseno and Quota.</p>	This is the latest release
^	
10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-2	A more recent release exists ^
<p>Citation: Office for National Statistics. Social Survey Division and Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency. Central Survey Unit, <i>Quarterly Labour Force Survey, January - March, 2011: Special Licence Access</i> [computer file]. 2nd Edition. Colchester, Essex: UK Data Archive [distributor], October 2012. SN: 6903, http://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-2</p> <p>Change log: 16 October 2012: For the second edition (October 2012), a new data file has been deposited, weighted to 2011 population figures. The documentation remains unchanged.</p>	
^	
10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-1	A more recent release exists ^
<p>Citation: Office for National Statistics. Social Survey Division and Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency. Central Survey Unit, <i>Quarterly Labour Force Survey, January - March, 2011: Special Licence Access</i> [computer file]. Colchester, Essex: UK Data Archive [distributor], December 2011. SN: 6903, http://dx.doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-6903-1</p> <p>Change log: 2 December 2011: DOI created</p>	

Figure 10. UKDA landing page for DOIs to longitudinal data

This is not the only way in which the UKDA handles longitudinal data. They have also implemented the Nesstar interface. Figure 11 shows this webtool, which allows researchers to discover, subset, analyse and download variables of interest from across longitudinal data, without having to download whole datasets. Top right shows where researchers are able to get a link that can be used to cite the exact subset of data extracted. While the UKDA are not currently minting DOIs to provide those links, it would be a possibility, both for the UKDA and for the MRC NSHD.

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The screenshot shows the UK Data Service webtool interface. On the left is a tree view of datasets, with 'Quarterly Labour Force Survey, January - March, 2011' selected. The main area displays the 'DESCRIPTION' tab for this dataset, showing 'Listwise Correlation analysis' options and a list of variables. A yellow box highlights the 'Choose variables from the browse list.' button. A URL box at the top right shows the page's address.

Figure 11. Quarterly Labour Force Survey data in the Nesstar webtool

The screenshot shows the 'Edit collection: Data Collection #851508' page in the UK Data Service ReShare repository. A breadcrumb trail at the top reads: Home → Legal → Review procedures → Terms and conditions → Award details → People → Data collection → Upload → Deposit. The page features a sidebar with navigation links (My data, Manage records, Profile, Review, Admin, Edit page phrases) and two main sections: 'Creators' and 'Copyright holders'. Each section contains a table with columns for Family name, Given name / Initials, Email, Affiliation, and ORCID, with three rows for creators and one row for copyright holders. An 'Add row' button is present below the creators table.

Figure 12. A data submission page showing where ORCID iDs can be included in the ReShare repository

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Both the ADS and UKDA maintain an authority record for creators and contributors that can be used to store a name identifier. Figure 12 shows part of the data submission process to the UKDA's ReShare repository, where the ORCID iDs of various contributors to the data can be added.

2.2.3. Archiving

The common workflow involves the creation of preservation and dissemination formats for the dataset files. In the case of retrospective assignment of identifiers, the data centre could facilitate a process of updating archived records with ORCID iDs and DOIs (see 2.3).

2.2.4. Dissemination and Access

At the point of dissemination, data are made available for reuse and citation. Data formats for dissemination may be different to formats for archiving. This will largely depend on whether the data are suitable for preservation and the common usage formats for the community. Specific advice for HSS archive and dissemination formats is given by the UKDA¹³.

Dissemination may include linking to publications and project web pages, citation in publications, and indexing of metadata by third parties¹⁴. Dissemination and reuse of data will be enhanced by the use of common identifiers and interoperable metadata.

2.3. Retrospective ORCID & DataCite linking

The original proof of concept workflows were developed in two parts: one workflow for the assignment of identifiers during the ingestion of new datasets, and another for the retrospective assignment of identifiers to archived datasets. The generic workflow needs to be flexible and accommodate both modalities, as repositories may implement a mixed approach.

In reality, the retrospective assignment of object identifiers is a two-step process: (i) minting the DOI and then (ii) updating the Archival Information Package with the DOI.

¹³ File formats & software: <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/format/formats>

¹⁴ One example being the Thompson Reuters Data Citation Index (http://wokinfo.com/products_tools/multidisciplinary/dci/)

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Once an archive takes the decision to use DOIs and sets up the required elements (a persistent landing page and mandatory metadata) the minting process can be implemented and actioned swiftly in a bulk process.

This is not the case with ORCID iDs, which must be added incrementally by the dataset creators; ideally such person identifiers would be included in the submission metadata. However, this is not always the case and if a repository decides to request person identifiers to enhance the quality of their archived data, they need to engage the creators in the process. In either case, the creator needs to have an identifier or be provided with the means to register for one, and then use an authenticated workflow to add the identifier to the dataset metadata.

ORCID web services can be integrated into the data submission process to enable authenticated collection of identifiers, and can also enable a retrospective claim process, through a search and link process. This allows authors to associate their datasets with their iD. The DataCite Metadata search tool developed in concert with the ODIN project supports this workflow. A challenge remained: for data repositories to update their archived data with the linked ORCID identifiers. This is possible, using an ODIN Codesprint-developed tool¹⁵ that searches ORCID for prefixes of interest and returns the ORCID iDs related to claimed DOIs. The Australian National Data Service has integrated this tool into their systems to enrich their metadata with ORCID iDs.

For the HEP proof of concept, adding identifiers is a bulk-update archiving process, similar to adding DOIs en masse to archived data. It is triggered upon request by the researchers themselves. From their author profiles, they are able to link their ORCID profile, allow INSPIRE to retrieve their list of publications from ORCID, or to push their INSPIRE claimed publication list to enhance their ORCID profiles.

HSS case studies were more wary of this process, because no further validations of claims meant they were reluctant to trust third-party metadata. The HSS proof of concept instead described an incremental approach to retrospectively linking datasets with creator ORCID iDs. So, where new a dataset is submitted with ORCID iDs or other personal or institutional identifiers, the relevant records within the creator authority file can have ORCID iDs appended.

¹⁵ http://wiki.datadryad.org/ODIN_CodeSprint

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The ADS has a similar process whereby a ‘people’ database acts as an authority file, so data submissions from one person link to the same record. This database includes a field for an ORCID iD captured during the submission process. It enables the ORCID iD submitted by depositors to be routinely checked by curators during the quality assurance process, which may not be feasible with bulk import from ORCID.

3. ANALYSIS RESULTS: COMMONALITIES AND DIFFERENCES

The proofs of concept in HSS and HEP demonstrate that it is possible for vastly different discipline data centres to share common processes for managing data and assigning identifiers. These processes remain common, even when different techniques are used to achieve them. Recognition of data production, curation, management and sharing are common goals across the research landscape, and so the DataCite and ORCID architectures and web services have been developed to facilitate this cross-discipline, multilateral adoption. Through the ODIN project services have evolved to increase interoperability further.

Even so, the technical implementations have identified some fundamental differences in the conceptual details of the repository. This includes, for example, whether a repository is an aggregating archive or receives direct deposits from researchers; whether it stores data in discrete data packages or as a large relational database.

3.1. Conceptual commonalities and differences in the workflows

Table 1 highlights a number of fundamental commonalities and differences between HSS and HEP data management processes. Importantly, though, while the differences may require specialised infrastructure for ingest or management of the data, only a small number of them actually affect the workflow for integration of object and personal identifiers developed by the proofs of concept. Key points requiring adaptation of the workflow follow.

HSS proof of concept has organizational authors

The ADS and UKDA both contain data where a creator or contributor to that data could be ‘institutional’. That is to say a research group or department, are the legitimate creators or contributors. This is not the case in HEP, where even for very large teams, contributors have different affiliations.

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Table 1. Conceptual and technical differences between proofs of concept

Conceptual differences between HEP and HSS proofs of concept (PoC)	Different approach?	Notes
HSS PoC has organisational authors	Y	Workflow is not affected, but systems need to use multiple identifier types
HEP PoC receives data from other repositories	N	Workflow remains the same
HEP PoC is an international repository, HSS PoC is national	N	Workflow remains the same
HSS PoC has rich subject-specific metadata	N	Workflow remains the same, only 5 fields are required for DOIs
HSS PoC quality assures data in detail (data can be rejected if it doesn't match the standards)	Y	All accepted objects receive PIDs, so workflow is unchanged, but metadata for people may require details on the type of input from each contributor
HSS PoC has rich subject-specific metadata	N	Workflow remains the same, only 5 fields are required for DataCite DOIs, but more are required for increased interoperability
HEP PoC objects may already have a persistent identifier	Y	Workflow may not always require an object identifier minting step
HEP PoC does not version data	N	Workflow remains the same, as HSS treats versions as discrete objects
HEP PoC receives harvested metadata in various formats. HSS PoC metadata is manually filled	N	Workflow remains the same

As a long-term study, funded on a project-by-project basis for fixed durations, and where employees have and will continue to change, the MRC NSHD need to be able to measure and demonstrate their impact over time. The result is that alternative creator and contributor identifiers are required. An alternative solution might be found in ORCID

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functionality released in December 2013. ORCID records can be linked to organisational identifiers, bounded by dates of association. This would allow ORCID iDs to be used to manage institutional impact, providing it is also possible to report on 'object - contributor - affiliation' sets of interest from the ORCID system.

A mixed model of individual and organisational identifiers would be the best starting approach for data repositories starting to develop their systems.

HSS proof of concept quality assures data in detail, and data can be rejected

All the HSS data repositories talked to so far provide a relatively large amount of internal quality assurance before data is published, including data cleaning, documentation and curation. Aside from the necessary infrastructure being in place, these repositories also employ skilled data curators/managers to perform this role.

This has implications for the metadata and assignment of personal identifiers. For instance, should data curators and managers critical to the process of making good quality data available have their own identifiers beyond those of the organisation that they work for? How are such organisations recognised for the investment in cleaning the data?

The quality assurance process is also the point at which a decision is made as to whether the data even receives a DOI. In the HSS examples, not all data automatically receives a DOI, for such reasons as embargos, incomplete data, and rejection of data. Similarly, in INSPIRE not all objects receive a DOI, but for a very different reason - some will already have an externally unique identifier.

HSS proof of concept has rich subject-specific metadata

There is a stark difference in the metadata between the HSS and HEP proofs of concept. Research data in HEP is very diverse and varies in complexity and so far not much data is shared or exchanged beyond the scope of an experiment. Data creators have not focused on standardised descriptions of their data and no metadata standard has been adapted to the needs of the HEP community. INSPIRE does endeavour to secure at least the mandatory metadata properties, as defined by DataCite, as well as additional optional ones. For example it stresses the usefulness of establishing a link between the publication and its accompanying data and adding as much descriptive metadata as possible to support discoverability.

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In contrast, the UKDA makes use of the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) metadata standards for the entirety of its data collection, since DDI is widely used to describe data from the social, behavioural and economic sciences.

Finally, regarding the sources from which metadata is harvested, INSPIRE collaborates with and harvests large quantities of data from several external research data centres, while the data hosted in the UKDA is from more heterogeneous sources, including individual researchers, research programmes, institutions and organisations, and government bodies.

3.2. Commonalities and differences beyond the proofs of concept workflow

The commonalities between the HEP and HSS proofs of concept also drive differences between them and the wider research landscape; see Table 2.

Table 2. Conceptual and technical differences beyond the proofs of concept

Further differences between proofs of concept and other known examples	Different approach?	Note
Proofs of concept are subject-specific, institutional repositories cover diverse subjects	N	Workflow remains the same
Objects in the proofs of concept have an externally unique PID, this may not be the case for all repositories	Y	PID minting stage may not be required
Creators and contributors to some data repositories will be non-academic	Y	Workflow is unchanged. Systems must use multiple ID types and personal IDs cannot be mandatory
Creators and contributors to some data repositories are staff internal to the repository. This is not the case for proofs of concept.	Y	Personal identifiers are known before data submission
Quality assurance practices may vary from repository to repository, some data may be rejected	N	Workflow remains the same

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Further differences between proofs of concept and other known examples	Different approach?	Note
Data from collaborations with industry may be archived but not shared	Y	PID minting stage may not be possible (sensitive metadata)
Subject-specific metadata schema are used where available	N	Workflow remains the same
Data in the proofs of concept is stored as discrete data files. In other repositories, received data may be amalgamated into a single data object (e.g. a relational database)	Y	Object PID minting at the usage point may need to be enabled

All objects in proofs of concept have an externally unique persistent identifier

While the proofs of concept aim to obtain an object identifier for all their data (whether from the third party supplier or applied by the repositories themselves), there are legitimate reasons for not applying a persistent identifier to all objects. This may apply especially to repositories holding data that is still being collected or updated, to repositories holding data that cannot be used externally for commercial or legal reasons and to data that is simply not in a citable form (e.g. image files with no metadata). In such cases the steps of assigning object identifiers are not relevant, or may need to be considered after ingest.

Creators and contributors to some data repositories will be non-academic

The origin of data is a key source of difference among data centres. The ADS for instance holds a large volume of data not generated by academics, but by commercial and local government authors. While an ORCID profile can be created based on their ADS data entries, the types of impact they are most driven by will tend not to be measured by citation; this aspect of disambiguation is not a major driver. There are potential drivers for personal identifier uptake in non-academic settings related to branding, tracking and of course discovery. But these are of less benefit to individuals than organisations (who may prefer to have organizational identifier attached to works) or end users. As a consequence, uptake of ORCID iDs or any other personal identifier is likely to remain slow in these communities.

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Creators and contributors to some data repositories are staff internal to the repository

The MRC NSHD varies from the proofs of concept particularly in the source of its data. Data are collected by researchers situated within the MRC NSHD, or by their close collaborators. Before the data can be used, third party researchers must be approved by and work closely with, an MRC NSHD employee. They are also required to submit any derived data back to the unit. As a result, the MRC NSHD has a high degree of control over personal identifiers, and is able to insist on and use them from the outset. Given personal identifiers are known before submission, the ORCID steps later in the workflow are less relevant. Such a situation is reflected in institutional repositories, who may have personal identifiers within their own internal management systems that can be attached to submissions to the repository. This may not be a complete solution though, since submissions to institutional repositories will include objects with contributors from other organisations that they do not have identifiers for.

Subject-specific metadata schema are used where available

While DDI metadata is used widely across the social sciences, the MRC NSHD does not explicitly use it. This is primarily because DDI was only established in 1995¹⁶ and, as the MRC NSHD does not routinely share its metadata with many third parties, changing their systems to use DDI has not been necessary. MRC NSHD variable level metadata is compatible with DDI, though not expressed as such in MRC NSHD documentation.

Data in the proofs of concept is stored as discrete data files. In other repositories, received data may be amalgamated into a single data object

The MRC NSHD and some other repositories, such as that illustrated in the mini case study or those using the NESSTAR platform¹⁷, do not store data in discrete data files in the way that the data was first collected, but as an amalgamation of data, for instance in a large relational database. An object identifier assigned to the large set of dynamic data may be appropriate for acknowledging its intellectual structure, but hinders reproducibility; cited data cannot be re-analysed accurately if it has been changed, or if only an undefined subset of a larger data object was used.

¹⁶<http://www.ddialliance.org/what/history.html>

¹⁷The Web View platform for NESSTAR (developed by the Norwegian Social Science Data Services) allows the download of subsets of data from aggregated data. <http://www.nesstar.com/software/webview.html>

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Mini Case Study: Sir Alister Hardy Foundation for Ocean Science

Sir Alister Hardy Foundation for Ocean Science (SAHFOS) a not-for-profit organisation that provides continuous plankton recorder data for oceanographic research.

This dynamic data is stored as a single data object. To enable reanalysis and verification of data, user requests for specific variables from the database are defined and cited as a subset.

Example:
SAHFOS; (2014): Plankton Data of the West Coast of Scotland; SAHFOS. <http://doi.org/10.7487/2014.49.1.11>

Figure 13. A mini case study for another way in which longitudinal data is managed

In such cases, the proposal from the Research RDA Citation working group¹⁸ is to assign identifiers to the subset as extracted and analysed by users (Pröll and Rauber, 2013). Providing the data can be reliably recalled, given the metadata required to assign a DOI, and a landing page, an identifier can be assigned at the point of discovery and access. This is the approach that the MRC NSHD is investigating.

3.3. Refining the generic workflow

Figure 14 shows the generic workflow refined and updated based on the cultural and technical differences explored.

The key adaptations that were made are:

- inclusion of a second possible object identifier step;
- acknowledgement of the reuse process feeding back into new data deposits; and,
- inclusion of steps to assess whether the mandatory metadata for the identified objects can be supplied at the set point in the process; whether the object as identified can be persistently provided; and, whether a human readable landing page can be created for that object on resolution of the identifier.

¹⁸ <https://rd-alliance.org/group/data-citation-wg.html>

Figure 14. Refined generic workflow

3.4. Applying the generic workflow

In adapting the workflow of a repository - or developing a workflow from scratch – two key intervention steps are required for greater discovery and interoperability:

- providing objects with externally unique and persistent identifiers; and,
- ensuring details of the creators of, and contributors to, data include personal identifiers.

These steps are broken down into further detail that determines how they are handled in the workflow.

3.4.1. Providing objects with externally unique and persistent identifiers

The first decision will be whether the data needs a persistent identifier. Specifically, will it already have one on ingest, and if so, is there a valid reason to assign an additional identifier?

If there is a valid reason to assign an identifier, then the second decision is, which type of identifier is appropriate for the data. This should include consideration of:

- identifiers already used within the community; and,
- whether within the use case, the requirements can be met for the selected identifier (e.g. technical support or system requirements, such as DataCite requiring mandatory, CC0 metadata and open landing pages).

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Figure 15. Characteristics of data and appropriate points in the workflow to assign identifiers

Once a decision has been made as to whether the requirements for the use of identifiers can be met, there is a linked decision: what to assign an identifier to. The data objects may be discrete items that are easily citable, or stored as a large amalgamation of data. They may be static or update over time. Once these questions have been answered the intervention point for assigning a persistent identifier can be located (illustrated in Figure 15).

3.4.2. Ensuring details of the creators and contributors to data include personal identifiers

In order to ensure the inclusion of personal identifiers in the contributor information received there are certain actions to consider. Specifically, there should be a step for the integration of personal identifiers within the data management workflow. The ideal point for associating identifiers should be with the submission metadata, but there should be forethought for possible system adjustments in case it is needed to integrate personal identifiers retrospectively. As above, if there is an identifier already widely accepted by the community its use would be preferable above the rest, and finally it should be ensured that the identifier is sent with the DataCite metadata. Of course, it should not be expected that every single user already has a personal identifier; or they may have one, but not the specific one that is endorsed. It would be beneficial to

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provide a quick link to the preferred service for acquiring an ID and general support for this matter, if possible.

3.4.3. Checklists

The following checklists gather the requirements and actions identified to include persistent identifiers as part as generic workflows. Object and personal identifiers facilitate greater discovery and interoperability, but demand a thoughtful implementation. Checklists help new integrators building the projects on the lessons learnt by the early adopters.

· **First considerations:** providing objects with externally provided unique and persistent identifiers.

1.	Is there a valid reason to assign persistent identifiers?
2.	Are there specific identifiers already used by the community?
3.	Can the requirements be met for each type of identifier? (a) regarding metadata (b) regarding long term preservation

· **Integration:** ensuring the platform and the integrators are prepared to develop the project.

1.	Will the integration cover the whole collection or only new objects?
2.	Is it possible to integrate identifiers retrospectively?
3.	Does the current platform support the use of persistent identifiers?
4.	Is software development necessary?
5.	Do integrators need training (or have a sufficient knowledge/experience)?

· **Workflows:** persistent identifiers should complement and enhance current workflows, and should block existing practices.

1.	Does a persistent identifier already exist for the object/person?
2.	Will the creation/submission of persistent identifiers be mandatory?
3.	Which metadata will be submitted to describe the object/person? (a) minimal requirement (b) further details
4.	Are metadata updates covered? How will they be triggered?
5.	How will the persistent identifiers be stored and displayed?
6.	How will be versions handled?

· **Community:** integrations should support the community providing enough information to understand and take advantage of it.

1.	Does the community understand the usage/value of persistent identifiers?
2.	Is there a plan in place to support and provide information about them?
3.	Could any of the new requirements block previously granted interactions?
4.	Are the new opportunities and benefits highlighted?
5.	Are the plans adapted to the different profiles (e.g. researchers, curators, users...)?

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Service provision support

4. HOW DOES ODIN SUPPORT SERVICE PROVISION IN THE DISCIPLINES?

Despite similar workflows, service provision details can diverge significantly among platforms. The type of service, the users' needs and technical constraints shape the integrations.

In High-Energy Physics, INSPIRE is the central platform for the community whereas Humanities and Social Sciences integrates multiples disciplines, with a diversity of needs. Looking beyond the proofs of concept, ODIN has supported two particular two particular case studies in HSS, ADS and MRC NSHD, as well as the technical development of INSPIRE as a centralised service provider for its community.

This section covers how the results of the first year and the generic workflows have supported the service provision and implementation of the case studies abovementioned. Similar characteristics and challenges are found in different disciplines. Both the First Year Event and the broad study carried out by WP5 show examples like geo- and life- sciences. ODIN results can guide such disciplines, by offering previous experiences and lessons learnt, towards a successful integration of persistent identifiers and enhancement of their services.

4.1. MRC National Survey of Health and Development

To test the proof of concept, we worked alongside the MRC NSHD¹⁹ towards integration of DOIs and name identifiers for their data.

4.1.1. Background

The MRC NSHD is a longitudinal cohort study of a sample of births in England Scotland and Wales during one week in March 1946. Participants have been studied 23 times in the intervening years, and the focus of the studies has changed through time: from physical and educational development; to the effects of childhood health on social

¹⁹ http://www.nshd.mrc.ac.uk/nshd_65/about_the_nshd.aspx

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circumstances in adulthood; and in recent years the factors influencing different health trajectories in aging.

In common with data held by the UKDA, the data held by MRC NSHD contains social, economic and health variables related to individuals. This makes the data sensitive, but it is not stored and accessed in the same way as UKDA data. Instead, MRC NSHD data is stored as a large aggregation of variables. Researchers who wish to make use of the data use an internal data discovery system (called SWIFT) to extract variables of interest into a 'basket' of data, which in turn is analysed for their specific research requirement(s). External researchers must first apply for access to MRC NSHD data through the existing data sharing and research governance procedures.

4.1.2. Data workflow

After the generic workflow outlined in Chapter 3 was developed, it was taken to the MRC NSHD and matched against their current processes. Figure 16 provides a sketch of their current workflow based on this discussion.

Figure 16. MRC NSHD current workflow

It is important to note that the MRC NSHD is not explicitly a general permanent archive for data, and so does not follow the OAIS model closely. In any case the OAIS model

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had not been developed when the MRC NSHD first began to collect and make data available in 1946. Even so, Figure 16 shows that there are clear parallels between MRC NSHD data processing and the generic workflow. The 'generate data', 'deposit data', 'ingest data' steps are analogous, although there are clear differences in how each happens.

Within MRC NSHD there are three distinct streams of data: core data, 'special' data and derived variables. All three are processed, managed and disseminated in the same way; their mode of origin differs. Initially, data is generated via data collection activities by researchers who are active members of the MRC NSHD itself: the core data. The data management and research teams work and are physically located together, and data generated there will ultimately be deposited within the MRC NSHD data repository. 'Special' data are data that have been collected by researchers external to MRC NSHD as part of a MRC NSHD data collection activity. This is typically data which requires external expertise or methods, such as biomedical imaging, genetics studies or geocoding. This will enter the MRC NSHD repository alongside a wave of core data collection.

MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing
MRC National Survey for Health and Development

Home	<p><i>Welcome to SWIFT, the Secure Web Interface For The LHA!</i></p> <p>The Medical Research Council (MRC) National Survey of Health of Development (NSHD) is an ongoing cohort study involving some 5,362 men and women born in England, Scotland and Wales who have been followed up since their birth in March 1946. Over the 60 year follow-up, study participants have provided personal information about their health and life circumstances and taken part in a wide range of tests of their physical, cognitive and mental health. Their right to privacy, and the ethical conduct of all researchers accessing the data, must be guaranteed.</p> <p>The scientific mission of the MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing (LHA), which manages the NSHD, is the discovery of life course influences on normal and healthy ageing, and the promotion of healthy ageing.</p> <p>SWIFT provides a means for researchers to access study data through a three-stage approval process.</p> <p>Read more about the study and the types of data it contains.</p> <p>Download an IEEE paper about the technical aspects of this project.</p> <p>Register now for access...</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Problems? Contact LHA SWIFT-LHA: Secure Web Interface For The LHA </p>
Register	
Login	
Enquiry	

Figure 17. The NSHD SWIFT interface

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final

To clarify the differences between MRC NSHD and the proofs of concept generic workflow at the dissemination stage, it is useful to describe the user experience of accessing the data. To access MRC NSHD data, a researcher must first complete a Formal Data Access Request form, shown in Figure 18. This form outlines their scientific objectives and the types of variables they required to meet these objectives. Data access requests are considered by an externally overseen Data Sharing Committee that meets on a monthly basis. If approved, a member of the MRC NSHD research team is assigned as an ‘internal consultant’; access is then granted to the MRC NSHD metadata system. The selected variables form a ‘basket of data’ that can then be downloaded and analysed. An example data basket view is shown in Figure 20. The variable level metadata view is also shown in Figure 21.

In the course of the analysis with a basket of data, further externally derived variables and associated algorithms and documentation may be created. As part of the permission to access MRC NSHD data, researchers are required to supply these externally derived variables back to the MRC NSHD to be made available alongside the core survey data. This highlights that where the previous proofs of concept were linear, MRC NSHD has a clear cyclical workflow. Derived variables from external researchers enter the ingest process to be added to the repository.

MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing
MRC National Survey for Health and Development

<p>Metadata Discovery</p> <p>Search</p> <p>View Basket</p> <p>Load/Share Basket</p> <p>Save Basket as New</p> <p>Overwrite Basket</p> <p>Shared Baskets</p> <p>Research Projects</p> <p>Review Projects</p> <p>Data Download</p> <p>Build Data File</p> <p>Download Data</p> <p>Account Management</p> <p>Update Details</p> <p>Change Password</p> <p>Logout</p>	<p>User p.curran logged in</p> <p>Level 2 Access - Search</p> <p>The NSHD metadata can be searched by keyword, year of collection or category, or a combination of all three search types.</p> <p>Please select your search type from the list below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Search by variable name only ▪ Search by keyword (including variable name and description) ▪ Browse by year of collection ▪ Browse by category ▪ Search by keyword and year ▪ Search by keyword and category ▪ Search by year and category ▪ Search by keyword, year and category ▪ Browse by library name <p>Note: SEX, INF and SERNO are added automatically to your basket.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="button" value="Back"/> <input type="button" value="Help"/> </p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Problems? Contact LHA SWIFT-LHA: Secure Web Interface For The LHA </p>
---	---

Figure 19. User view of variable-level search options in MRC NSHD’s SWIFT system

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final 38/90

MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing
MRC National Survey for Health and Development

Metadata Discovery User p.curran logged in

Search

View Basket

Load/Share Basket

Save Basket as New

Overwrite Basket

Shared Baskets

Research Projects

Review Projects

Data Download

Build Data File

Download Data

Account Management

Update Details

Change Password

Level 2 Access - Shopping Basket

Variable	Remove?
INF	X
SERNO	X
SEX	X
WOPAF05	X
WOPQL05	X
WOPY105	X
WOPY205	X
WOPY305	X
WOPY405	X
WOPY505	X

[Remove all variables from basket](#)

[Save this basket as new](#)

[Overwrite an existing basket](#)

Figure 20. An example of a ‘basket’ of variables - subset data of interest - in the MRC NSHD SWIFT system

MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing
MRC National Survey for Health and Development

Metadata Discovery User p.curran logged in

Search

View Basket

Load/Share Basket

Save Basket as New

Overwrite Basket

Shared Baskets

Research Projects

Review Projects

Data Download

Build Data File

Download Data

Account Management

Update Details

Change Password

Logout

Level 2 Access - Variable Metadata

Variable Metadata:

Name	WOPAF05
Description	What were the main ways in which the operation to remove your uterus and/or ovaries affected your wellbeing and quality of life?
Year	2005 Questionnaire, Summary
Form	Postal Questionnaire 2005
Question Number	6

[Add to basket](#)

Value Labels:

Value	Label
1	Specify main ways in which operation to remove uterus and/or ovaries affected wellbeing and quality of life
7	No questionnaire
8	Not applicable

Category Memberships:

[Women's health](#)

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
COLS48	3556	1	3	1.551	.880
Valid N (listwise)	3556				

EQ - demographic variables - COLS48

Figure 21. NSHD metadata system, user view of variable-level metadata

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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4.1.3. Metadata sharing

MRC NSHD metadata is not stored in the social science standard DDI-L, but is mapped to DDI-L, and, in the small number of cases where NSHD has and will share its metadata, DDI-L is used. MRC NSHD currently share study-level metadata and some collection-event-level metadata, with the MRC Research Data Gateway for Population and Health Studies²¹, a discovery platform for MRC-funded longitudinal studies and their data. Figure 22 shows the study level metadata and Figure 23 shows collection-event metadata within the Research Data Gateway (the Gateway). The Gateway does not hold data from any of the 34 MRC funded studies in its metadata repository. Instead, researchers must make an application through the existing governance processes of the studies participating in the Gateway. Although data is pseudonymised, it is treated as sensitive and is only available through the MRC NSHD Data Sharing Committee described above.

Figure 22. The MRC NSHD record within the MRC Research Data Gateway

²¹ <https://www.datagateway.mrc.ac.uk/>

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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The screenshot shows the MRC Research Data Gateway interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with links like Home, Search, Browse Studies, Timeline, About, Contact, Forums, Help, and Request Account. Below this is a search bar where 'National Survey of Health and Development' has been entered. The search results section displays two items: 'Age 4' and 'Age 53', both identified as 'Data Collection Event' metadata. The 'Age 4' result includes a brief description: 'circumstances of the mother and baby, questionnaire 1950 National Survey of Health and Development (NSHD) ...' and a date '2012-01-13 00:10'. The 'Age 53' result includes: 'Health and Development (NSHD) ... and exercise habits and experience of disturbing life events, questionnaire 1999 National Survey of ...' and a date '2011-12-01 17:23'. On the left side, there are filters for 'Current search' (2 items found), 'Filter by content type' (Data Collection Event), and 'Filter by nshd' (NSHD (2)). There's also a 'Sort by' section with options for Relevancy, Title, and Type.

Figure 23. NSHD collection event metadata within the MRC Research Data Gateway

A further layer has been added as the MRC NSHD is contributing to the CLOSER programme²². The CLOSER programme aims to link and harmonise the results of UK longitudinal research. MRC NSHD currently plans to submit DDI metadata to CLOSER for inclusion in its integrated search platform. Again, due to the sensitive nature of the data, CLOSER will not hold any data, but will enable metadata searching and link to the holding study, which include MRC NSHD.

4.1.4. Integrating identifiers

Discussions with MRC NSHD on the best way of integrating identifiers, found three key goals, to be able to:

²² <http://www.closerprogramme.co.uk> CLOSER is the Cohort and Longitudinal Studies Enhancement Resource, a consortium of nine cohort and longitudinal studies, funded by ESRC and MRC and working to improve awareness of and increase usage of such studies. An integrated search platform and harmonized variables are being developed to support these aims.

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- assign DOIs in a manageable way that meets DataCite requirements;
- assign DOIs in a way to provide them and their funders with the easiest way of monitoring NSHD data impact; and to,
- use name identifiers to identify the MRC NSHD ‘team’, as well as non-active researchers (including retired and deceased).

Based on discussion of these concerns, the key points for integrating data and personal identifiers were identified and are shown on an updated version of the MRC NSHD workflow in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Updated version of the MRC NSHD Workflow

Object identifiers

In a marked difference between the MRC NSHD workflow and the proofs of concept, there is a case for a second point of DOI assignment. The data baskets generated by external researchers are a small subset of the MRC NSHD data, but the need to identify such baskets to allow replication and verification of research findings is a clear use case for a distinct identifier from the original survey data.

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This was not observed in the original proofs of concept, but is already practiced by some data archives currently assigning DOIs to their data²³ and has been recommended by the Research Data Alliance working group on Data Citation (dynamic data)²⁴. This is especially relevant for data centres which hold very dynamic data or those which hold large aggregations of data that are subset by users prior to reuse.

Further internal discussion at MRC NSHD concluded that this approach, while promising, has the potential to generate thousands of DOIs, which would be unmanageable. Their preference is for a small number of DOIs corresponding to the major data types forming a single data collection. This would also be much simpler for their funders to monitor for impact. So, although assigning DOIs to 'baskets' of data will not be taken forward by the study management, it has still been included in the generic workflow.

Person identifiers

For the MRC NSHD as well as for other HSS repositories, clear identification and disambiguation of organisational identifiers is essential. Their systems need to be flexible enough to accept more than one kind of author or contributor identifier.

At the time of writing the MRC NSHD is not considering an extensive ORCID integration, beyond accepting ORCID iDs within the metadata. Those ORCID iDs will provide suitable author disambiguation. As the MRC NSHD data comes from internal contributors and collaborators, it is relatively simple for them to request ORCID iDs at ingest and incorporate these into their metadata. An organisational ID for the unit could be included when sending metadata to third parties as well, but may not need to be permanently held within local systems.

As the core MRC NSHD data is generated by an in-house research team, enforcing inclusion of ORCID iDs to documentation is a relatively simple step. Current researchers and team members can be asked to obtain an ORCID iD, and records kept of the iDs to be added into subsequent documentation; getting an ORCID iD can be part of induction for new team members. As special data is created in close collaboration with external

²³ One example being the Sir Alister Hardy Foundation for Ocean Science (SAHFOS), shown in Figure 11.

²⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/data-citation-making-dynamic-data-citable-wg-update.html>

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researchers, supply of ORCID iDs can be made a requirement for the data documentation. To ensure that externally derived variable data include ORCID iDs, it may be possible to request that one is supplied at the Formal Data Access Request form stage; this is a minor addition and step compared to what is already requested. Once derived variables are returned by external researchers, ORCID iDs will already be known and can be included in documentation.

4.2. The UK Archaeology Data Service

The UK Archaeology Data Service (ADS) was an early adopter of DataCite DOIs in the UK. Adoption of DOIs contributed to the ADS being awarded Best Archaeological Innovation 2012 at the British Archaeological Awards. This case study summarises and updates one prepared for the British Library's DataCite service²⁵, and is included as a humanities example, as well as a further sense-check of the workflows and processes.

4.2.1. Background

The ADS is an open access repository of digital archaeological outputs. These outputs include objects ranging from text documents to spreadsheets, 3D and remote sensing data. Objects are generally part of an 'archive' that represents the outputs of an archaeological investigation. As the archaeological process is usually a destructive one, the data may be the only record of a site available to future research.

In addition to these archives, the ADS hosts the Grey Literature Library²⁶. This library makes 20,000 previously unpublished field reports available online. These field reports are largely unpublished fieldwork from commercial archaeological investigations.

4.2.2. Integrating object identifiers

To manage the retrospective assignment of DOIs to the backlog of ADS material, a custom script was written to take the landing page of completed archives, automatically generate a DOI and send requests to the DataCite API to mint these DOIs in bulk.

²⁵ Working with the British Library and DataCite. Institutional Case Studies: http://www.bl.uk/aboutus/stratpolprog/digi/datasets/DataCiteCaseStudies_2013.pdf

²⁶ ADS Grey Literature Library: <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archives/view/greylit/>

For new submissions, there are two paths of data ingest to the ADS. One is researcher submission to the ADS archive; the other is ColdFusion transfer of grey literature reports from a third party in to the Grey Literature Library. For a representation of the workflow see Figure 25.

Figure 25. Archaeology Data Service workflow²⁷

Direct research submissions to the archive are accompanied by a project-level metadata template filled in by the submitter. ADS metadata²⁷ is based on an extended Dublin Core schema²⁸ and Dublin Core itself maps closely to the DataCite Schema²⁹. As part of the ingest process, these are input into the archive and quality checked by an ADS in-house digital archivist. An archivist's view of ADS metadata is shown in Figure 26.

²⁷ ADS: Creating metadata records for datasets: <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/depositCreate3#section-depositCreate3-2.3.1.CreatingMetadataRecordsForDatasets>

²⁸ Dublin Core Metadata Initiative: <http://dublincore.org/>

²⁹ Mapped in DataCite Metadata Schema v. 2.2: [doi:10.5438/0005](https://doi.org/10.5438/0005)

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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The ADS also performs digital curation prior to minting a DOI. The curator chooses when the data is ready and then triggers the assignment of a DOI within the collection management system. The archivist's view of assigning DOIs to ADS datasets is shown in Figure 27. DOIs For the grey literature library, where objects come from an intermediate source (OASIS³⁰) via ColdFusion transfer, the script for retrospective assignment of DOIs was adapted to be integrated into the transfer process.

Implementation of the DataCite API allowed integration of identifier assignment into existing workflows.

ADS Collection Management System

[Home](#) [Tracking](#) [Collections](#) [People](#) [Admin](#) [Project Docs](#) [Advice](#) [Advanced Search](#) [ADS-easy](#) | [OASIS](#) | [Logout](#)

search collections

Burdale: an Anglo-Saxon settlement on the Yorkshire Wolds (Collection Id: 1001596)

Tracking (1004114) | Collection (1001596)

DOI
Metadata
DataCite

This is the current metadata for the active DOI (10.5284/1021540) related to this archive. For previous versions of the metadata for this DOI, go to the [DataCite MDS](#).

Creator(s):	Julian D Richards Steve Roskams	Julian D Richards Steve Roskams
Title:	Burdale: an Anglian settlement in the Yorkshire Wolds	Burdale: an Anglian settlement in the Yorkshire Wolds
Publication Year:	2013	2013
Subject(s):	AGRICULTURE AND SUBSISTENCE [Monument Type (England)] DEFENCE [Monument Type (England)] INDUSTRIAL SITE [Monument Type (England)] FIELD SYSTEM [Monument Type (England)] INDUSTRIAL [Monument Type Class] ENCLOSED SETTLEMENT [Monument Type (England)]	ENCLOSED SETTLEMENT [Monument Type (England)] FIELD SYSTEM [Monument Type (England)] INDUSTRIAL SITE [Monument Type (England)] INDUSTRIAL [Monument Type Class] DEFENCE [Monument Type Class] AGRICULTURE AND SUBSISTENCE [Monument Type Class]
Contributor(s):	Julian D Richards [Copyright holder]	Julian D Richards [RightsHolder]
Alternate Identifier:	1596	1596
Related Identifier(s):		
Version:	1	1
Description:	Investigation into night-hawk activity in Burdale dry valley revealed an Anglian assemblage of 8th-9th century date, consistent with a 'productive site'. Aerial photography demonstrated the presence of 'Butterwick' type irregular enclosures. Archaeological fieldwork was subsequently undertaken as a University of York training excavation in order to characterise the nature of the activity. The archive comprises the primary data and reports from field-walking, geophysical survey, and excavation.	Investigation into night-hawk activity in Burdale dry valley revealed an Anglian assemblage of 8th-9th century date, consistent with a 'productive site'. Aerial photography demonstrated the presence of 'Butterwick' type irregular enclosures. Archaeological fieldwork was subsequently undertaken as a University of York training excavation in order to characterise the nature of the activity. The archive comprises the primary data and reports from field-walking, geophysical survey, and excavation.

[\[UPDATE\]](#)

Figure 26. ADS digital archivists' view of ADS internal metadata and metadata sent to DataCite, within the collection management system

³⁰ Online Access to the Index of Archaeological Investigations: <http://oasis.ac.uk>

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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ADS Collections Management System

Tracking Collections **DOIs** People Organisations Addresses Admin Logout

search DOIs

Wroxeter Conservation Plan (Collection Id: 1001166)
[See this archive on-line](#)

[Go to Tracking Project \(1003607\)](#) | [Go to Collection \(1001166\)](#)

DOI	Metadata	DataCite
DOI:	10.5284/1017083	
Landing Page:	http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archives/view/wroxcons_eh_2012 [UPDATE]	
[MINT]		

Archaeology Data Service, Department of Archaeology, The King's Manor, University of York, York, YO1 7EP

Figure 27. ADS digital archivists view of the collection management system. Tab for assigning and updating DOIs

4.2.3. Integrating personal identifiers

The ADS have adapted their collection management database to hold ORCID iDs for creators of submitted data. They now routinely ask depositors for ORCID iDs and include them in metadata sent to DataCite where possible. This integration was simple, but ADS has observed low uptake of ORCID iDs in the non-academic sectors.

Figure 28 shows the archivists' view of a person's record within the ADS. It displays basic details of that person, such as contact information and ORCID iD. The object records related to that person are also shown, alongside that person's role in each object. In the selected example, the author Julian Richards, the ADS has two different author records with that name, who are separate individuals. The ORCID iD is particularly useful to differentiate them.

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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[ADS-easy](#) | [OASIS](#) | [Logout](#)

search people, organisations, addresses | add / link person, organisation, address

Person Details (Julian D Richards): i

[Edit Person Details](#)

Person Id:	21
Title:	Prof
First Name:	Julian D
Last Name:	Richards
ORCID ID:	0000-0003-3938-899X
Status:	Active
Deceased Year:	
Std:	01904
Phone:	433901
Fax:	433902
Email:	julian.richards@york.ac.uk
Position:	
Department:	Department of Archaeology
Preferred Org / Address:	Archaeology Data Service, King's Manor
Added:	10-Aug-2009, jim
Updated:	21-Nov-2013, py523

Organisations / Addresses associated with the Person:

Person	Organisation	Address
Richards, Julian D, Prof	Archaeology Data Service	King's Manor, Exhibition Square, York, , YO1 7EP, England
Richards, Julian D, Prof	University of York	King's Manor, Exhibition Square, York, , YO1 7EP, England
Richards, Julian D, Prof		i Person with Richards ... 0000 0003

Tracking Projects associated with this Person:

Tracking Project	Person Role(s)
Anglian and Anglo-Scandinavian Cottam: linking digital publication and archive (Internet Archaeology 10) (collection 1001424)	Copyright holder, Creator, Depositor, Hosting institution, Licence Signed By, Primary contact, Publisher
Anglian and Viking Settlement in Northumbria	Funder, Primary contact
Anglo-Saxon Landscape and Economy: using portable antiquities to study Anglo-Saxon and Viking Age England (Internet Archaeology 25) (collection 1001284)	Contributor, Contributor, Copyright holder, Creator, Depositor, Primary contact, Publisher
Anglo-Saxon Landscape and Economy: using portable antiquities to study Anglo-Saxon and Viking England (collection 1000848)	Copyright holder, Creator, Creator, Creator, Depositor, Funder, Licence Sent To, Licence Signed By, Primary contact
Archaeological Evaluation of the Anglo-Saxon and Viking site at Torksey Lincolnshire (collection 1001383)	Creator, Creator, Depositor, Funder, Funder, Initial Contact By, Licence Sent To, Licence Signed By
ARIADNE	Co-Investigator
Burdale: An Anglian Settlement in the Yorkshire Wolds (Data Paper) (Internet Archaeology 35)	Contributor, Contributor, Copyright holder, Creator, Initial Contact By, Licence Sent To, Licence Signed By, Primary contact, Publisher
Burdale: an Anglo-Saxon settlement on the Yorkshire Wolds (collection 1001596)	Copyright holder, Creator, Creator, Depositor, Depositor, Hosting institution, Initial Contact By, Licence Sent To, Licence Signed By, Primary contact
Burrow House Farm - Cottam (collection 1000312)	Copyright holder, Creator, Depositor, Funder, Primary contact
Contexts of Learning: The PATOIS project and Internet-based teaching and learning in Higher Education (Internet Archaeology 12) (collection 1001401)	Copyright holder, Creator, Creator, Creator, Creator, Depositor, Primary contact, Publisher
Cottam A: a Romano-British and Anglian Settlement in East Yorkshire (collection 1000994)	Copyright holder, Creator, Depositor, Funder, Hosting institution, Licence Sent To, Licence Signed By, Primary contact

Figure 28. An archivists' view of a person's record within the ADS's content management system

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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The ADS collection management system assigns a number of roles to people for each archive. At present these are:

- Co-Investigator
- Contributor
- Copyright holder
- Creator
- Depositor
- Fieldworker
- Funder
- Hosting institution
- Initial contact by
- Licence sent to
- Licence signed by
- Originator
- Primary contact
- Principal investigator
- Publisher
- Technical contact
- Web contact

Some of them are administrative roles that are useful to the ADS, but may not be relevant in a wider context for acknowledgement and credit around the data.

Figure 29 shows the simple functionality that ADS implemented, allowing users to navigate to the ORCID records of creators that are associated with an ORCID iD. This is the landing page for an object displayed in the Julian Richard's record in Figure 28.

The screenshot shows the ADS website interface. At the top is the ADS logo and a search bar. Below is a navigation menu with links like HOME, ARCHSEARCH, ARCHIVES, LEARNING, ADS-easy, ADVICE, OUR RESEARCH, BLOG, ABOUT US, and LOGIN. A secondary menu lists categories like JOURNALS AND SERIES, GREY LITERATURE, PROJECT ARCHIVES, BIBLIOGRAPHIES, and THESES. The main content area features the title 'Cottam A: a Romano-British and Anglian Settlement in East Yorkshire' by Julian D Richards, 2011. On the left, there are links for Introduction, Overview, Downloads, Metalwork query, and Coins query. A link to the creator's ORCID record is visible. The right side contains an 'Introduction' section with a list of project aims and a photograph of the excavation site. The University of York logo is at the bottom left.

Figure 29. An ADS record showing the link between a creator and their ORCID record.

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final

The ADS have internal organisational identifiers and will be using these to enable further discovery of data via organisations. The problem remains, though, of how to encourage adoption of externally unique identifiers by organisations where there is a lack of clear benefit, especially for non-academic organisations, in uptake.

4.3. INSPIRE

INSPIRE is an information hub of numerous resources. Built on top of the Invenio³¹ digital library software, INSPIRE aggregates and hosts the main body of the HEP literature and provides it to the community via comprehensive scientific records based on the MARC21 standard. At present it holds more than 1,000,000 publications that are linked to author information and data, if available.

INSPIRE's code is Open Source and publicly available. The different branches, covering the Invenio software under the platform, INSPIRE's overlay and multiple tools are available in GitHub³².

4.3.1. PIDs for data in INSPIRE

A prerequisite for assigning a DataCite DOI is the provision of five mandatory metadata elements. From a metadata perspective, the MARC-based fields used by INSPIRE are matched with the version 3.0 of DataCite's Metadata XML Schema³³. However, as the community starts sharing special types of research output, such as standalone data, it is imperative to focus on these new metadata needs by including more detailed metadata, primarily for discoverability and preservation purposes.

INSPIRE's source for preprints is arXiv³⁴, a repository of e-prints of scientific publications operated by Cornell University, from which HEP-related articles are being harvested daily. The end product is records that are not restricted to presenting preprints or published papers, but which integrate other supplementary materials. This is supported by several features that add value to the services (e.g. citation tracking), further analysed in 4.3. Published papers are fed into the system by publishers and

³¹ <http://invenio-software.org>

³² <https://github.com/inspirehep>

³³ DataCite Metadata Schema 3.0 XML Schema. doi:[10.5438/0009](https://doi.org/10.5438/0009)

³⁴ <http://arxiv.org/>

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final 50/90

SCOAP3³⁵, the Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics, which “has converted key journals in the field of High-Energy Physics to Open Access at no cost for authors”.

Table 3. Mapping DataCite mandatory metadata to MARC

DataCite’s Schema	INSPIRE’s MARC fields
Identifier	0247_2, 0247_A
Creator	100__A, 700__A
Title	245__A
Publisher	260__B
Publication Year	269__C, 773__T, 961__X, 260__C

Other than these direct submissions, INSPIRE harvests data from a variety of sources. Durham University’s data repository, HepData³⁶, has been integrated with INSPIRE and has so far provided approximately 55.000 datasets corresponding to HEP publications [7]. Data also comes to INSPIRE from two other data repositories, the Harvard Dataverse Network³⁷ and Figshare³⁸ (Figure 30).

The workflow and data architecture for integrating research data into INSPIRE requires careful attention. Reliable, thoroughly thought-through approaches are essential, especially when the aim is for large numbers of datasets (including very large datasets) to be easily and openly shared, cited and reused. The use of permanent and unique identifiers is a crucial element of this process. Since data is received from many different sources it is anticipated that some dataset metadata will already include one or more persistent identifiers, and that in contrast, some may not have any PID assigned. Not all cases will require new PIDs to be minted and many datasets do not include any PIDs as part of the metadata, as is the case for unpublished material. INSPIRE manages those differences by providing unified PID ingestion, update and storage of

³⁵ <http://scoap3.org>

³⁶ <http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/>

³⁷ The Dataverse Network Project: <http://thedata.org>

³⁸ <http://figshare.com>

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the metadata. Below we describe how INSPIRE manages data integration depending on whether the data has been previously assigned a PID or not. It is also possible to have a PID from a third party service, as it happens in the example of the GitHub³⁹ → Zenodo⁴⁰ → INSPIRE integration in chapter 4.3.2, where code is pushed from Github to INSPIRE through Zenodo.

Figure 30. INSPIRE as an information hub

4.3.1.1. Data with PIDs

To make sure that this process is performed properly, the BibCheck module⁴¹ is used to resolve issues such as PID duplicates, since it is able to automatically run several types of tests on the incoming metadata, fix errors and adjust elements that do not satisfy the quality standards. Should a delicate case arise, it generates an alert so the case is fixed manually by the curators. The process is shown in Figure 31.

³⁹ <http://github.com>

⁴⁰ <http://zenodo.org>

⁴¹ BibCheck is an Invenio module. It checks a set of records against a configurable set of rules.

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)

Version: 1_0 Final

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```
""" Bibcheck plugin add the DOIs (from crossref) """
from invenio.bibrecord import record_add_field
from invenio.crossrefutils import get_doi_for_records
from invenio.bibupload import find_record_from_doi

def check_records(records, doi_field="0247_a", extra_subfields =
                    (("2", "DOI"),)):
    """
    Find the DOI for the records using crossref and add it to the
    specified field.
    This plugin won't ask for the DOI if it's already set.
    """
    records_to_check = {}
    for record in records:
        has_doi = False
        for position, value in record.iterfield("0247_2"):
            if value.lower() == "doi":
                has_doi = True
                break
        if not has_doi:
            records_to_check[record.record_id] = record
    dois = get_doi_for_records(records_to_check.values())
    for record_id, doi in dois.iteritems():
        dup_doi_recid = find_record_from_doi(doi)
        if dup_doi_recid:
            record.warn("DOI %s to be added to record %s already
                        exists in record/s %s" % (doi, record_id,
                                                    dup_doi_recid))
            continue
        record = records_to_check[record_id]
        subfields = [(doi_field[5], doi.encode("utf-8"))] +
                    map(tuple, extra_subfields)
        record_add_field(record, tag=doi_field[:3],
                        ind1=doi_field[3], ind2=doi_field[4],
                        subfields=subfields)
        record.set_amended("Added DOI in field %s" % doi_field)
```

Figure 31. Code snippet: Bibcheck plugin, validating on duplicate DOIs using Crossref

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Figure 32 shows an example of data initially submitted to Dataverse. Dataverse assigned the PID (a Handle in this case) for the data, which was then sent to INSPIRE. The data was added to the record of the original paper on INSPIRE, in the data tab. The complete record for this data is shown in Figure 33. It is important to note that the data record has a link to the original publication record and vice versa, and that the INSPIRE record has also kept the citation recommendation from the original Dataverse record. Generally, including a citation recommendation in a data record allows direct citation, which means that a specific dataset can be cited rather than only the paper that the dataset accompanies.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a Dataverse record. At the top, it says 'Harvard Dataverse Network > CFA Dataverses >' and 'POWERED BY THE Dataverse Network PROJECT v. 3.6.2'. The main title is 'Kyle Cranmer Dataverse'. Below that, it says 'REPLICATION DATA FOR: "NATURAL PRIORS, CMSSM FITS AND LHC WEATHER FORECASTS"' and provides the handle 'hdl:1902.1/21804' and version information. There are tabs for 'CATALOGING INFORMATION', 'Data & Analysis', 'Comments (1)', and 'Versions'. The 'Data Citation' section contains a citation recommendation: 'Cranmer, Kyle; Allanach, Ben; Lester, Christopher; Weber, Arne, "Replication data for: "Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts"', http://hdl.handle.net/1902.1/21804 UNF:5:bvw2MoOATltXOyfGjF9hJQ== V1. [Version]'. Below this is a 'Citation Format' dropdown and a 'Print' button. The 'Original Publication' section states: '"Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts", JHEP 0708:023,2007. DOI 10.1088/1126-6708/2007/08/023 ID: DOI:10.1088/1126-6708/2007/08/023 Link'. At the bottom, there is a 'Data Citation Details' section with a table:

Title	Replication data for: "Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts"
Study Global ID	hdl:1902.1/21804
Authors	Cranmer, Kyle (New York University); Allanach, Ben (Cambridge U., DAMTP); Lester, Christopher (Cambridge U.); Weber, Arne (Munich, Max Planck Inst.)

Figure 32. A dataset hosted by the Dataverse Network, uses a Handle as a PID

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HEP :: HEPNAMES :: INSTITUTIONS :: CONFERENCES :: JOBS :: EXPERIMENTS :: JOURNALS :: HELP

Information Citations (0) Files

Replication data for: "Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts"

Cranmer, Kyle (New York U.); Allanach, Ben (Cambridge U., DAMTP); Lester, Christopher (Cambridge U.); Weber, Arne (Munich, Max Planck Inst.)

Cite as: Cranmer, Kyle; Allanach, Ben; Lester, Christopher; Weber, Arne, "Replication data for: "Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts"", <http://hdl.handle.net/1902.1/21804>

Description: MCMC scan of CMSSM used in "Natural Priors, CMSSM Fits and LHC Weather Forecasts". The entry is tabular data with named rows. Minimal analysis is available via the browser. Except from the original web-page that hosted this data. 10 independent files. Each one is a statistically independent sampling of the posterior. The density of points in parameter space is proportional to the posterior probability of the point. The fits are described in the paper, and have had the dark matter, (g-2), mu, B_s->mu mu, MW, sin^2 theta_1, mt, mb, alphas, BR(b->s gamma) and sparticle/Higgs direct search limits applied to them. Each point in the sample is a line of the file, organised into a list of numbers, in the following order: The weight of the point - you *must* take this into account if you're doing Bayesian stats. An integer specifying the number of parameters to come m0/GeV m1/2/GeV A0/GeV tan beta mb(mb) MSbar/GeV mt/GeV alpha_s(MZ) MSbar/GeV alpha(MZ) MSbar sign mu m_gluino/GeV m_chargino1/GeV m_stau_1/GeV mselectron_R/GeV msquark_L/GeV mstop_1/GeV msbottom_1/GeV msneutrino_1/GeV mh^0/GeV mA/GeV omega_{DM} h^2 (g-2)_mu BR(b->s gamma) m_neutralino_1/GeV BR(B_s->mu mu) m_neutralino_2/GeV sin^2 theta_1^eff MW/GeV irrelevant irrelevant irrelevant irrelevant sigma(LHC QCD sparticle production)/pb sigma(LHC gaugino production)/pb sigma(LHC slepton production)/pb mu parameter/GeV m3squared parameter/GeV^2 ln(posterior) (overall normalisation)

Preview not available

Note: * Temporary entry *

This dataset complements the following publication:
[Natural priors, CMSSM fits and LHC weather forecasts](#)

Record created 2013-07-26, last modified 2013-09-11

Figure 33. The same Dataverse record on INSPIRE, using the same PID and citation recommendation

The ingest of datasets coming from Figshare is carried out in the same way. But this case also highlights the importance of carefully following the citation recommendations of different services. As shown in Figures 34 and 35, Figshare's citation recommendation includes the retrieval date. This modification is not yet implemented in INSPIRE.

Neither the HSS proof of concept, nor the further HSS case studies currently receive data that already has a persistent identifier. This is because their data are largely submitted directly by research teams and have not been stored in another repository. Some streams, such as the grey literature ingested into the ADS, may potentially include persistent identifiers in the future but as this is not an imminent issue, there is currently no technical means to deal with it. However, the rules applied in the Bibcheck module could be applied in automatic or manual checks when data with persistent identifiers starts to be deposited.

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The screenshot shows a Figshare dataset page. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Browse', 'Upload', 'Sign up', and 'Login'. The main title is 'Supplementary Material for "A Novel Approach to Higgs Coupling Measurements"'. Below the title, there is a list of files with 'preview' and 'download' links for each. A 'Download all' button is located below the list. On the right side, there are statistics: '250 views', '3 shares', and a 'cites coming soon' badge. Below these are the publication date 'Published on 31 Dec 2013 - 02:18 (GMT)' and the total file size 'Filesize in total is 829.03 KB'. There are sections for 'Categories' (Particle Physics), 'Authors' (Kyle Cranmer, Sven Kreiss), 'Tags' (Higgs, likelihood, LHC), and 'License' (what's this?). At the bottom, there is a 'Share this:' section with social media icons and an 'Embed' button, and a 'Cite this:' section with the citation text and DOI link.

Figure 34. A dataset in Figshare, it uses a DOI as the PID of the record

The screenshot shows the same dataset on the INSPIRE website. The top navigation bar includes 'HEP :: HEP NAMES :: INSTITUTIONS :: CONFERENCES :: JOBS :: EXPERIMENTS :: JOURNALS :: HELP'. Below the navigation bar, there is a 'Welcome to INSPIRE' message. The main content area has tabs for 'Information', 'Citations (1)', and 'Files'. The title is 'Supplementary Material for "A Novel Approach to Higgs Coupling Measurements"'. Below the title, there is a list of authors: 'Cranmer, Kyle (New York University); Kreiss, Sven (New York University)'. The 'Cite as:' section shows the citation text and the DOI link: 'Cranmer, Kyle; Kreiss, Sven (2013): Supplementary Material for "A Novel Approach to Higgs Coupling Measurements". figshare. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.888607>'. The 'Description:' section contains the text: 'Supplementary material including the toy model used for Section 4 and a Mathematica notebook to explicitly perform calculations in Appendix A.' Below the description, there is a note: 'This dataset complements the following publication: [A Novel Approach to Higgs Coupling Measurements](#)'. At the bottom, there is a note: 'Record created 2014-03-07, last modified 2014-03-19'.

Figure 35. The same Figshare dataset on INSPIRE, keeps the DOI but the citation recommendation still shows the old format

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4.3.1.2. Data without PID

HepData [2] is the biggest dataset source for INSPIRE. It serves around 55.000 datasets extracted from 8.000 publications in HEP. The repository has been running since 1970, hosted by Durham University.

The Durham HepData Project

REACTION DATABASE • DATA REVIEWS • PDF PLOTTER

ABOUT HEPDATA • SUBMITTING DATA

Enter query: Search

examples: re gamma gamma%, re p p --> p p and obs sig, exp cern

Search Help -- Output Help -- Form Search -- Browse Keywords -- Latest LHC DATA

To search the database:
Enter your query command comprising keyword-value pairs joined with Boolean ANDs. A null entry will retrieve all records. Use % as the right or left truncation character to search for values beginning or ending with the value. All searches are case-insensitive. More details are in the Search Help.

The basic hepdata keywords are:
 reac - the reaction (e.g. p p -> charged x), also beam, targ, and fsp.
 obs - the observable (e.g. SIG, DSIG/DX, DN/DPT).
 sqrts - the centre-of-mass energy in GeV.
 exp - the experiment/laboratory name (e.g. ZEUS, CERN, LHC).
 date - the year of the publication/preprint.
 auth - the first author name on the paper.
 ref - the publication/preprint reference.

Searching via 'Inspire':
 title: word (matches Inspire records having 'word' in the paper title).
 keyword: word (matches Inspire records having 'word' in the inspire keywords).
 author: name (matches Inspire records having 'name' in the author list).

HepData data reviews

- **NEW** Quarkonia data in Hadronic Interactions
- Structure functions in DIS
- Single photon production in hadronic interactions
- Two-photon reactions leading to hadron final states
- Drellian cross-sections
- Inclusive particle production data in e+e- interactions
- Hadronic total cross-sections (R) in e+e- interactions
- Low-energy neutrino cross-sections
- Event shapes in lepton-lepton and lepton-nucleon interactions

HepData @HepData 20h
Updated uncertainties for @ATLASpapers data on "Measurement of dijet cross sections in pp collisions at 7 TeV" at hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/view/ins1266975
[Expand](#)

HepData @HepData 20h
Added @FermilabToday E907 MIPP data on "Measurement of Charged Pion Production Yields off the NuMI Target" to hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/view/ins1291947
[Follow @HepData](#)

Contact us at: [hepdata\(at\)projects.hepforge.org](mailto:hepdata(at)projects.hepforge.org)

HepData is funded by the UK STFC and hosted at the Durham IPPP.
HepData also maintains the UK mirror of the PDG.

IP3 Science & Technology Facilities Council

Figure 36. The HepData repository frontend

Its data model is based on the concept of Paper, where each one of the Datasets are objects representing plots or tables of the publication. The metadata describing the content is located at the Paper level, and makes each Dataset a lower class citizen containing only the necessary fields to store the content of the tables.

HepData's data model is not compatible with INSPIRE's and the views of other services, where datasets should be first class citizens, with their own metadata and description. Such difference has forced INSPIRE to develop an ad-hoc solution to harvest and represent HepData records that presents many technical difficulties.

Furthermore, HepData does not provide an open and standardised API, so the only way to extract the available information is directly parsing the HTML pages served by the system. To allow such approach, INSPIRE developed a harvester tool that requests and

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process the information slowly, as it used to saturate the service. Some examples are shown by the code snippets in Figures 37 to 38:

```
def download_with_retry(data_url):
    last_e =None
    sleeptime=2
    for retry_num in xrange(5):
        try:
            f= urllib2.urlopen(data_url)
            content= f.read()
            return content
        except Exception, e:
            last_e = e
            time.sleep(sleeptime)
            sleeptime= sleeptime *2
    raise Exception("Failed to download url. Last error code: %s"%
                    (last_e.code,))
```

Figure 37. Code snippet: Slow requests, doubles the time between requests every time to avoid overloading the server.

```
def wash_code(content):
    """
    Correcting the HEPData XHTML code so that it can be parsed\
    @return correct code - string
    """
    #filtering out cases of having incorrect closing tags containing attributes
    res= re.split("</([a-zA-Z0-9]+)\s[^>]*>", content)
    for pos in range(1, len(res), 2):
        res[pos] = "</"+ res[pos] + ">"
    content="".join(res)
```

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```

# in the systematics section there are errors with enclosing colspans in
# quotes
res= re.split("colspan=([0-9]+)\'", content)
for pos in range(1, len(res), 2):
    res[pos] ="colspan='"+ res[pos] + "'"
    content="" .join(res)
return content

```

Figure 38. Code snippet: Cleans incorrect HTML code before trying to parse it.

The original plan included the creation of DOIs for each one of the datasets hosted by HepData. But the previously described issues, in particular the mismatch of the data model, do not allow a persistent, stable and well described DOI assignment. HepData, with the support of the INSPIRE collaboration, is currently considering the possible options of migrating its platform to a new, more compatible and modern technology. It is a challenging project, given the lack of technical support and knowledge in the field, and the investment and resources necessary to migrate the service.

The screenshot shows the INSPIRE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HEP, HEP NAMES, INSTITUTIONS, CONFERENCES, JOBS, EXPERIMENTS, JOURNALS, and HELP. Below this, a search bar and a welcome message are visible. The main content area displays a dataset entry titled "Data from Figure 7 from: Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector at the LHC". The entry includes the ATLAS Collaboration as the author, a citation as "ATLAS Collaboration (2013) HepData, http://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.26B4.TY5F", and a description: "-2 log Likelihood for the H→ WW*→ lν channel in the (μ_{ggF+tH} * B/BSM, μ_{VBF+VH} * B/BSM) plane for a Higgs boson mass m_H = 125.5 GeV." A note indicates it is a temporary entry and provides a link to the publication. The record was created on 2013-09-11 and last modified on 2013-12-16.

Figure 39. Higgs Boson datasets, from HepData with an INSPIRE DOI

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)

Version: 1_0 Final

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As a proof of concept, INSPIRE minted DOIs for a small and controlled subset of HepData’s material. Figure 39 shows one of them, the data behind the discovery of the Higgs Boson by the ATLAS collaboration at CERN. This dataset has a DOI and has already been cited by four different publications, successfully tracked by INSPIRE.

This is an example on how the model matches the needs of the researchers in the field, and how, with the appropriate standard technologies, all HepData’s collection could better serve the HEP community and foster data reuse. The project opened a discussion in the HEP community about data citation and re-use (Figure 40).

2D likelihoods: the ATLAS case

ATLAS $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma, WW, ZZ$

Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector at the LHC

ATLAS Collaboration (Georgios Aad et al.) | [arXiv:1307.7132](#)

Jul 4, 2013 - 32 pages

Phys.Lett. B726 (2013) 88-119 (2013)
 DOI: 10.1016/j.physleta.2013.08.010
 CERN.PH.EP.2013.103
 e-Print: arXiv:1307.7132 [hep-ex] | PDF
 Experiment: LHC/LHC-ATLAS

Abstract (arXiv)
 Measurements are presented of production properties and couplings of the recently discovered Higgs boson in the $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ channel. The $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ signal is observed in the 4ℓ and $4\ell + 2\gamma$ channels at center-of-mass energies of 7 TeV and 8 TeV, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 36.1 and 20.3 fb⁻¹, respectively. The $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ signal is observed in the 4ℓ and $4\ell + 2\gamma$ channels at center-of-mass energies of 7 TeV and 8 TeV, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 36.1 and 20.3 fb⁻¹, respectively. The $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ signal is observed in the 4ℓ and $4\ell + 2\gamma$ channels at center-of-mass energies of 7 TeV and 8 TeV, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 36.1 and 20.3 fb⁻¹, respectively. All measurements are consistent with expectations for the Standard Model.

$\mu_{ggH+ttH}$	μ_{VH+VBF}
1.8300000e+00	2.2500000e+00
1.8820000e+00	2.2500000e+00
1.9340000e+00	2.2500000e+00
1.9860000e+00	2.2500000e+00
2.0380000e+00	2.2500000e+00
2.0900000e+00	2.2500000e+00
2.1420000e+00	2.2500000e+00
2.1940000e+00	2.2500000e+00
2.2460000e+00	2.2500000e+00

Digitized version of the experimental likelihood

Jeremy Bevan | LHC Higgs Cross Section Working Group 1

a leap forward

[...] the ATLAS collaboration has taken an important step forward by making the likelihood function for three key measurements about the Higgs available to the world digitally. [K. Cranmer, QuantaDiaries, 12-Sep-2013]

INSPIRE

Data from Figure 7 from: Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector at the LHC

ATLAS Collaboration (Georgios Aad et al.) | [arXiv:1307.7132](#)

Cite as: ATLAS Collaboration (2013) HepData, [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-9826-9_10](#)

Description: 2 log Likelihood for the $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ channel in the $(\mu_{ggH+ttH}, \mu_{VH+VBF})$ plane for a Higgs boson mass $m_H = 125.5$ GeV.

Note: *Temporary entry*

This dataset complements the following publication:
 Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states at the ATLAS detector at the LHC

Figure 7

Figure 40. Researchers show their interest in data re-use and citation

HepData, as the main data platform in HEP, is the natural place to store datasets and provide that service to the community. Most of the HEP Collaboration submits their content there but, as it is manually included, a big backlog of submissions must be processed in order to keep the service up to date. Given that problem, and for the specific case of members in the HEP community interested in obtaining a DOI for their datasets, INSPIRE, via ODIN, has stepped in to support data submission (Figure 41).

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New dataset/code submission

Dataset Information:

Title:

Supplements the publication: (DOI, arXiv ID, INSPIRE record ID, title... or empty for standalone data)

Author names: (empty to inherit the same authors as the paper)

Description:

Upload file:

Assign a DOI to the dataset? (example: 10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.1234.5678)
 Yes
 No

Contact Information:

Your name:

Your e-mail address:

Figure 41. Simple data submission form

The process has been also designed to allow software citation, assigning DOIs to pieces of code that researchers can reuse. Figure 42 shows a group of implementations submitted directly to INSPIRE, with their DOIs and citation recommendations:

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
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DATASETS:

Description: This is the MadAnalysis 5 implementation of the CMS search for top-squark pair production in the single lepton final state with 19.5/fb at 8 TeV, to be used for re-interpretation studies. The C++ code contains extensive comments and can thus easily be used as a template for implementing other analyses.

Note: This analysis requires MINUIT libraries. Therefore, the line `<LIBFLAGS += -lminuit>` should be added to the Makefile of the Build/ directory before compilation. More information how to use this code as well as a detailed validation summary are available at <http://madanalysis.irmp.ucl.ac.be/wiki/PhysicsAnalysisDatabase>

Cite as: Dumont, B., Fuks, B., Wymant, C. (2014) MadAnalysis 5 implementation of CMS-SUS-13-011: search for stops in the single lepton final state at 8 TeV. doi: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.LR5T.2RR3](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.LR5T.2RR3)

[Go to the record](#)

Description: This is the MadAnalysis 5 implementation of the ATLAS search for third-generation squarks in final states with 0-leptons and two b-jets, with 20.1/fb at 8 TeV, to be used for re-interpretation studies.

Note: Information how to use this code as well as a detailed validation summary are available at <http://madanalysis.irmp.ucl.ac.be/wiki/PhysicsAnalysisDatabase>

Cite as: Chalons, G. (2014) MadAnalysis 5 implementation of ATLAS-SUSY-2013-05. doi: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.Z4ML.3W67](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.Z4ML.3W67)

[Go to the record](#)

Description: This is the MadAnalysis 5 implementation of the ATLAS search for direct production of charginos, neutralinos and sleptons in final states with two leptons and missing transverse momentum with 20.3/fb of data at 8 TeV, to be used for re-interpretation studies.

Note: Information how to use this code as well as a detailed validation summary are available at <http://madanalysis.irmp.ucl.ac.be/wiki/PhysicsAnalysisDatabase>. The ATLAS analysis is documented at <https://atlas.web.cern.ch/Atlas/GROUPS/PHYSICS/PAPERS/SUSY-2013-11/>

Cite as: Dumont, B. (2014) MadAnalysis 5 implementation of ATLAS-SUSY-2013-11: di-leptons plus MET. doi: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.HLMR.T56W](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP.DATA.HLMR.T56W)

Figure 42. Software re-use and citation, INSPIRE suggests all datasets that extend a paper

HepData’s equivalent software platform is called HepForge, and contains an extensive list of legacy and under development HEP projects. As with HepData, it does not provide a particular centralised API, and is a challenging project for future integrations.

The current lack of a centralised software service, together with the establishment of well-known platforms, such as GitHub, is leading many researchers to distribute their software using third-party services. Further initiatives in that regard, in particular the GitHub → Zenodo → INSPIRE integration, are covered in the next sections of this document.

4.3.1. PIDs for authors in INSPIRE

ORCID iDs are able to resolve several author related challenges in INSPIRE, and should ideally be collected during the data ingest process.

In the HEP field it is not unusual for large collaborations, consisting of thousands of researchers, to be listed as authors of a single publication or dataset. This phenomenon

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)

Version: 1_0 Final

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is known as “hyperauthorship” [12]. A paper produced by the ATLAS collaboration would require about 3000 scientists to sign it as authors, resulting in problems when it comes to managing the information of every individual author (Figure 43). For such cases a data ingest workflow must be adapted to the possibility of such extensive metadata.

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Information References (93) Citations (0) Files Plots

Measurements of spin correlation in top-antitop quark events from proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV using the ATLAS detector

ATLAS Collaboration (Georges Aad (Marseille, CPPM) *et al.*) [Show all 2883 authors](#)

Jul 16, 2014 - 20 pages

CERN-PH-EP-2014-116
e-Print: [arXiv:1407.4314](https://arxiv.org/abs/1407.4314) [hep-ex] | PDF

Abstract (arXiv)
Measurements of spin correlation in top quark pair production are presented using data collected with the ATLAS detector at the LHC with proton-proton collisions at a center-of-mass energy of 7 TeV, corresponding to an

Measurements of spin correlation in top-antitop quark events from proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV using the ATLAS detector

ATLAS Collaboration (Georges Aad (Marseille, CPPM), Brad Abbott (Oklahoma U.), Jalal Abdallah (Taiwan, Inst. Phys.), Samah Abdel Khalek (Orsay, LAL), Ovsat Abidinov (Baku, Inst. Phys.), Rosemarie Aben (FOM, Amsterdam), Babak Abi (Oklahoma State U.), Maris Abolins (Michigan State U.), Ossama AbouZeid (Toronto U.), Halina Abramowicz (Tel Aviv U.), Henso Abreu (Technion), Ricardo Abreu (CERN), Yiming Abulaiti (Stockholm U. & Stockholm U., OKC), Bobby Samir Acharya (INFN, Udine & ICTP, Trieste & King's Coll. London), Leszek Adamczyk (AGH-UST, Cracow), David Adams (Brookhaven), Jahred Adelman (Yale U.), Stefania Adomeit (Munich U.), Tim Adaye (Rutherford), Tatjana Agatonovic-Jovin (Belgrade U.), Juan Antonio Aguilar-Saavedra (LIP, Lisbon & CAFPE, Granada), Marco Agustoni (Bern U., LHEP), Steven Ahlen (Boston U.), Faig Ahmadov (Dubna, JINR & Baku, Inst. Phys.), Giulio Aielli (INFN, Rome & Rome U., Tor Vergata), Henrik Akerstedt (Stockholm U. & Stockholm U., OKC), Torsten Paul Ake Åkesson (Lund U.), Ginga Akimoto (Tokyo U., ICEPP), Andrei Akimov (Lebedev Inst.), Gian Luigi Alberghi (INFN, Bologna & Bologna U.), Justin Albert (Victoria U.), Solveig Albrand (LPSC, Grenoble), Maria Josefina Alconada Verzini (La Plata U.), Martin Aleksa (CERN), Igor Aleksandrov (Dubna, JINR), Calin Alexa (Bucharest, IFIN-HH), Gideon Alexander (Tel Aviv U.), Gauthier Alexandre (Geneva U.), Theodoros Alexopoulos (Natl. Tech. U., Athens), Muhammad Alhroob (INFN, Udine & Udine U.), Gianluca Alimonti (INFN, Milan), Lion Alio (Marseille, CPPM), John Alison (Chicago U., EFI), Benedict Allbrooke (Birmingham U.), Lee John Allison (Lancaster U.), Phillip Allport (Liverpool U.), John Almond (Manchester U.), Alberto Aloisio (INFN, Naples & Naples U.), Alejandro Alonso (Bohr Inst.), Francisco Alonso (La Plata U.), Cristiano Alpignani (Queen Mary, U. of London), Andrew David Altheimer (Nevis Labs, Columbia U.), Barbara Alvarez Gonzalez (Michigan State U.), Mariagrazia Alviggi (INFN, Naples & Naples U.), Katsuya Amako (KEK, Tsukuba), Yara Amaral Coutinho (Rio de Janeiro Federal U.), Christoph Amelung (Brandeis U.), Dante Amidei (Michigan U.), Susana Patricia Amor Dos Santos (LIP, Lisbon & Coimbra U.), Antonio Amorim (LIP, Lisbon & Lisboa U., CFNUL), Simone Amoroso (Freiburg U.), Nir Amram (Tel Aviv U.), Glenn Amundsen (Brandeis U.), Christos Anastopoulos (Sheffield U.), Lucian Stefan Ancu (Geneva U.), Nansi Andari (CERN), Timothy Andeen (Nevis Labs, Columbia U.), Christoph Falk Anders (Heidelberg U.), Gabriel Anders (CERN), Kelby Anderson (Chicago U., EFI), Attilio Andreazza (INFN, Milan & Milan U.), George Victor Andrei (Kirchhoff Inst. Phys.), Xabier Anduaga (La Plata U.), Stylianos Angelidakis (Athens U.), Ivan Angelozzi (FOM, Amsterdam), Philipp Anger (Dresden, Tech. U.), Aaron Angerami (Nevis Labs, Columbia U.), Francis Anghinolfi (CERN), Alexey Anisenkov (Novosibirsk, IYF), Nuno Anjos (LIP, Lisbon), Alberto Annovi (Frascati), Ariadni Antonaki (Athens U.), Mario Antonelli (Frascati), Alexey Antonov (Moscow Phys. Eng. Inst.), Jaroslav Antos (Kosice, IEF), Fabio Anulli (INFN, Rome), Masato Aoki (KEK, Tsukuba), Ludovica Aperio Bella (Birmingham U.), Rudi Apolle (Oxford U. & Rutherford), Giorgi Arabidze (Michigan State U.), Ignacio Aracena (SLAC), Yasuo Arai (KEK, Tsukuba), Juan Pedro Araque (LIP, Lisbon), Ayana Arce (Duke U.), Jean-Francois Arguin (Montreal U.), Spyridon Argyropoulos (DESY), Metin Arik (Bogazici U.), Aaron James Armbruster, Olivier Arnaez (CERN), Vanessa Amal (Madrid, Autonoma U.), Hannah Arnold (Freiburg U.), Miguel Arratia (Cambridge U.), Ozan Arslan (Bonn U.), Andrei Artamonov (Moscow, ITEP), Giacomo Artoni (Brandeis U.), Shoji Asai (Tokyo U., ICEPP), Nedaa Asbah (DESY), Adi Ashkenazi (Tel Aviv U.), Barbro Åsman (Stockholm U. & Stockholm U., OKC), Lily Asquith (Argonne), Ketevi Assamagan (Brookhaven), Robert Astalos (Comenius U.), Markus Atkinson (Illinois U., Urbana), Naim Bora Atlay (Siegen U.), Benjamin Auerbach (Argonne), Kamil Augsten (Prague, Tech. U.), Mathieu Auroseau (Johannesburg U.), Giuseppe Avolio (CERN), Georges Azuelos (Montreal U. & TRIUMF), Yuya Azuma (Tokyo U., ICEPP), Max Baak (CERN), Alessandra Baas (Kirchhoff Inst. Phys.), Cesare Bacci (INFN, Rome & Rome III U.), Henri Bachacou (IRFU, Saclay), Konstantinos Bachas (Aristotle U., Thessaloniki), Moritz Backes, Malte Backhaus (CERN), John Backus Mayes (SLAC), Elisabeta Badescu (Bucharest, IFIN-HH), Paolo Bagiacchi, Paolo Bagnaia (INFN, Rome & Rome U.), Yu Bai (Beijing, Inst. High Energy Phys.), Travis Bain (Nevis Labs, Columbia U.), John Baines (Rutherford), Oliver Keith Baker (Yale U.), Petr Balek (Charles U.), Fabrice Balli (IRFU, Saclay), Elzbieta Banas (Cracow, INP), Swagato Banerjee (Wisconsin U., Madison), Arwa A E Bannoura (Wuppertal U.), Vikas Bansal (Victoria U.), Hardeep Singh Bansil (Birmingham U.), Liron Barak (Weizmann Inst.), Sergei Baranov (Lebedev Inst.), Elisabetta Luigia Barberio (Melbourne U.), Dario Barberis (INFN, Genoa & Genoa U.), Marlon Barbero (Marseille, CPPM), Teresa Barillari (Munich, Max Planck Inst.), Marcello Barisonzi (Wuppertal U.), Timothy Barklow (SLAC), Nick Barlow (Cambridge

Figure 43. Hyperauthorship, around 3000 authors sign the ATLAS collaboration publications.

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final 63/90

Another person-related challenge is the prevalence of common names in INSPIRE, where the same signature can apply to many individuals (Table 4).

Table 4. Count of the most repeated names in INSPIRE

Signature	Instances
Zhang, J.	1515
Abe, K.	1457
Eigen, G.	1429
Li, J.	1368
Davier, M.	1323
Liu, Y.	1281
Banerjee, S.	1267
Wu, J.	1263
Lafferty, G.D.	1260
Patel, P.M.	1256

For the purpose of managing all the name information in a structured and user friendly way, INSPIRE conducted extensive user testing and used the feedback to develop new author profile page, summarising the information about a HEP scientist. This found (Figure 44) that the main users of the system are interested in three types of information regarding authors, and indicated how the content display could be improved.

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
	WP3: Proofs of concept		Dissemination level: PU
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Figure 44. User testing results after a Card Sorting exercise with the users of INSPIRE.

INSPIRE’s new author profiles redesign has three columns (Figure 45). The left column provides personal information about the scientist (affiliations, collaborations etc.) and a list of their connected external IDs, most notably their linked ORCID iD.

The centre column provides the list of outputs list, showing the entire scientist’s INSPIRE publications in one tab and the datasets they have produced in another tab. A third tab hosts external publications that are not included in INSPIRE, but have originated from their linked ORCID profile. Statistics on citations are gathered in the right column.

INSPIRE uses DOIs to track citations, so if a paper is cited by other papers it is tracked and the information is shown in the citations summary. DOIs are also used to avoid processing information twice, thus ensuring that publications or data coming from other systems (such as ORCID) are not already in INSPIRE and thus should be added to a profile.

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

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Cranmer, Kyle S.

Profile Name

[View Profile](#) [Manage Profile](#) [Manage Publications](#) [Ayuda](#)

2014-07-15 13:30:58

PERSONAL INFORMATION

PUBLICATIONS AND OUTPUT

STATS

Personal Details (HEPNAMES)

Name Kyle S. Cranmer
Current Institution New York U.
E-mail cranmer@cern.ch
Links <http://physics.as.nyu.edu/~obje...>
<http://twitter.com/KyleCranmer...>
<http://theoryandpractice.org/>

Fields HEP-EX
HEP-PH
PHYSICS

Experiments FINAL-E-0830
CERN-LHC-ATLAS
CERN-LEP-ALEPH
FINAL-TEV-CDF

Identifiers BAI: K.S.Cranmer.1
INSPIRE: INSPIRE-00074922
ORCID: 0000-0002-5769-7094
ARXIV: ARXIV:CRANMER-K-1

Period	Rank	Institution
1995 - 1999	UG	Rice U.

Publications Datasets External

1. Measurement of differential production cross-sections for a Z boson in association with b-jets in 7 TeV proton-proton collisions with the ATLAS detector.
2. Search for contact interactions and large extra dimensions in the dilepton channel using proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV with the ATLAS detector.
3. Flavour tagged time dependent angular analysis of the $B_s \rightarrow J/\psi\phi$ decay and extraction of $\Delta\Gamma$ and the weak phase ϕ_s in ATLAS
4. Search for new phenomena in the dijet mass distribution using pp collision data at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV with the ATLAS detector.
5. Observation of an Excited B_c^{++} Meson State with the ATLAS Detector
6. Measurement of the $t\bar{t}$ production cross-section as a function of jet multiplicity and jet transverse momentum in 7 TeV proton-proton collisions with the ATLAS detector
7. Measurement of the cross-section of high transverse momentum vector bosons reconstructed as single jets and studies of jet substructure in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV with the ATLAS detector
8. Search for pair-produced third-generation squarks decaying via charm quarks or in compressed supersymmetric scenarios in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV with the ATLAS detector
9. Search for supersymmetry in events with large missing transverse momentum, jets, and

Co-Authors

W.Wiedenmann.1 (423)
M.P.Casado.1 (421)
E.E.Kluge.1 (419)
P.Hanke.1 (419)
G.D.Cowan.1 (414)
C.Goy.1 (411)
J.Neisen.1 (411)
K.Jakobs.1 (411)
A.M.Litke.1 (410)
D.Palini.1 (410)

Papers

	All papers	Single authored
All papers	485	10
Book	0	0
ConferencePaper	29	8
Introductory	0	0
Lectures	0	0
Published	383	2
Review	5	0
Thesis	1	1

Citations Summary

485 papers found, 474 of them citeable (published or arXiv)

	Citeable papers	Published only
Number of papers analyzed:	474	383
Number of citations:	35133	32805
Citations per paper (average):	74	85
h_{wp} index [?]	81	80

Breakdown of papers by citations:

	Citeable papers	Published only
Renowned papers (500+)	8	7
Famous papers (250-499)	10	10
Very well-known papers (100-249)	44	42
Well-known papers (50-99)	105	104
Known papers (10-49)	190	179
Less known papers (1-9)	83	39
Unknown papers (0)	34	2

[Click here to view statistics without self-citations or RPP](#)

Warning: The citations count should be interpreted with great care. [Read the fine print](#)

Figure 45. New Author Profile Pages

Finally, many editing functions are provided in the “Manage Profile” and “Manage Publications” tabs, such as linking an arXiv account with an INSPIRE profile, merging profiles, and so on.

Figure 46 shows the linkage between INSPIRE and ORCID. The link is automatic using OAuth if the user is logged in, in any other case, it triggers a manual check A bi-directional information exchange will soon be in place; users will be able both pull their publication list from ORCID, and push information from INSPIRE to ORCID. This additional functionality is under test and will be deployed soon. Figure 46 shows how the interface will look:

ORCID

This profile has not been connected to an ORCID account yet.

Suggest an ORCID for this profile:

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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	Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_0 Final 66/90

Figure 46. Mock-ups for the ORCID push

Pushing content to ORCID using its API is relatively easy, provided there is a group of dedicated developers. However, the management of duplicates and versions generates different difficulties. ORCID does not use a de-duplication tool, and each one of the services pushing content is supposed to compare and avoid them. This procedure can be automated only if PIDs are available and shared between all the services.

ORCID is in the process of developing a means to compare metadata and group linked objects using PIDs. The goal is to prevent import of duplicates from the same sources, and to group apparent duplicates from different sources, thus easing the previously described issues.

4.3.1.1. INSPIRE's services

INSPIRE integrates all its resources and is committed to building added-value services on top to benefit the community.

“In-house” services

INSPIRE is planning to create an open Data Collection, in order to offer the same search services as for the publications. The first step in its development was to user-

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test its interface as data has different characteristics and requires different search approaches. One of the most common requests by the researchers was to keep a clear and direct link to the original publication as well as other reuses of the data, to provide the background and context.

The data records include a direct link back to the publication, following the structure “This dataset complements the following publication(s)”. From the paper to the dataset, a “data tab” is proposed, where a short description of each dataset, plus a general overview, will simplify the information extraction (Figure 47).

This dataset complements the following publication:
[Exclusive \$J/\psi\$ photoproduction off protons in ultra-peripheral p-Pb collisions at \$\sqrt{s_{NN}}=5.02\$ TeV](#)

The screenshot shows a web interface with tabs for Information, References, Citations, Files, Plots, and Data. The main content area displays the title of the publication, the ALICE Collaboration authors, and a link to the arXiv preprint. Below the title, it states 'THIS DATA COMES FROM DURHAM HEPDATA PROJECT'. A 'SUMMARY:' section follows, containing a detailed description of the experiment and results. A 'DATASETS:' section is also present, with a 'Description:' field providing further details about the dataset. A 'Go to the record' link is located at the bottom of the dataset description.

Figure 47. Linkage between publications and datasets

Users also demanded a different search interface to group results in the same context. Figures 48 and 49 show the difference between the current style and the proposed alternative based on the test results.

	D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality		
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higgs Search Advanced Search

None

Sort by: Display results: Output format:
 latest first desc - or rank by - 25 results single list Brief format

Data 38 records found 1 - 25 jump to record: 1 Search took 0.07 seconds.

- Additional data from: Search For Higgs Boson Pair Production in the gamma gamma b bbar Final State using pp Collision Data at sqrt(s)=8 TeV from the ATLAS Detector**
 ATLAS Collaboration
[References](#) | [BibTeX](#) | [LaTeX\(US\)](#) | [LaTeX\(EU\)](#) | [Harvmac](#) | [EndNote](#)
[Detailed record](#)
- Additional data from: Search For Higgs Boson Pair Production in the gamma gamma b bbar Final State using pp Collision Data at sqrt(s)=8 TeV from the ATLAS Detector**
 ATLAS Collaboration
[References](#) | [BibTeX](#) | [LaTeX\(US\)](#) | [LaTeX\(EU\)](#) | [Harvmac](#) | [EndNote](#)
[Detailed record](#)
- Additional data from: Search for dark matter in events with a hadronically decaying W or Z boson and missing transverse momentum in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s}=8$ TeV with the ATLAS detector**
 ATLAS Collaboration
[References](#) | [BibTeX](#) | [LaTeX\(US\)](#) | [LaTeX\(EU\)](#) | [Harvmac](#) | [EndNote](#)
[Detailed record](#)

Figure 48. Current result style

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higgs Search Advanced Search

None

Sort by: Display results: Output format:
 latest first desc - or rank by - 25 results single list Brief format

Data 33 records found 1 - 25 jump to record: 1 Search took 0.07 seconds.

- Data from: Fitting the Phenomenological MSSM**
 Shehu S. AbdusSalam, Benjamin C. Allanach (Cambridge U., DAMTP), Fernando Quevedo (Cambridge U., DAMTP & CERN), Farhan Feroz, Mike Hobson (Cambridge U.). Apr 2009. 70 pp.
 Published in *Phys.Rev. D81* (2010) 095012
The Posterior Sample Points' SLHA Files from the Bayesian Fits of the Phenomenological MSSM [Dataverse]
 Description: The Posterior Sample Points' SLHA Files from the Bayesian Fits of the Phenomenological MSSM (pMSSM) to indirect collider and dark matter data. The for the pMSSM and the fitting of the parameters are described in the publications. Each of the SLHA files passed all the constrains from dark matter, electroweak [...] DOI: [10.7910/DVN/22742](https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/22742)
[Detailed record](#)
- Data from: Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector**
 ATLAS Collaboration
 Published in *Phys.Lett. B726* (2013) 88-119
Figure 7 (1/3) [HepData]
 Description: -2 log Likelihood for the $H \rightarrow WW \rightarrow l\nu l\nu$ channel in the $(\mu_{ggF+tH} * B/BSM, \mu_{VBF+VH} * B/BSM)$ plane for a Higgs boson mass $m_H = 125.5$ GeV.
 DOI: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA.26B4.TY5F](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA.26B4.TY5F)
[Detailed record](#) - Cited by 2 records
Figure 7 (2/3) [HepData]
 Description: -2 log Likelihood for the $H \rightarrow ZZ \rightarrow 4l$ channel in the $(\mu_{ggF+tH} * B/BSM, \mu_{VBF+VH} * B/BSM)$ plane for a Higgs boson mass $m_H = 125.5$ GeV.
 DOI: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA_RF5P.6M3K](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA_RF5P.6M3K)
[Detailed record](#) - Cited by 2 records
Figure 7 (3/3) [HepData]
 Description: -2 log Likelihood for the $H \rightarrow ZZ \rightarrow 4l$ channel in the $(\mu_{ggF+tH} * B/BSM, \mu_{VBF+VH} * B/BSM)$ plane for a Higgs boson mass $m_H = 125.5$ GeV.
 DOI: [10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA_RF5P.6M3K](https://doi.org/10.7484/INSPIREHEP_DATA_RF5P.6M3K)
[Detailed record](#) - Cited by 2 records

Figure 49. Proposed result style

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)

Version: 1_0 Final

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The current implementation generates further challenges. In particular, there is a diverse variety of datasets, with different types of metadata to search. For example, HepData records inherit parts of their metadata from publications (due to the data model differences already outlined) while Figshare and Dataverse have them directly as first class citizens. Given Invenio's architecture, it implies different types of queries (direct and cross-collection).

One of the major services of INSPIRE is citation tracking. This is an almost unique service, able to extract references, link them to the correct publication in the database and transfer the information to extract citation statistics for the author profiles. PIDs enable data citation tracking; researchers have already started including references to data, which INSPIRE is tracking effectively, as Figure 50 shows.

Information Citations (4) Files

Data from Figure 7 from: [Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector at the LHC](#) - ATLAS Collaboration (for the collaboration)

Cited by: 4 records

- (16) [On the presentation of the LHC Higgs Results](#) - Boudjema, F. *et al.* arXiv:1307.5865 [hep-ph]
- (5) [A Novel Approach to Higgs Coupling Measurements](#) - Cranmer, Kyle *et al.* arXiv:1401.0080 [hep-ph]
- (4) [Les Houches 2013: Physics at TeV Colliders: New Physics Working Group Report](#) - Brooijmans, G. *et al.* arXiv:1405.1617 [hep-ph]
- (1) [Constraints on Higgs Couplings and Physics Beyond the Standard Model](#) - Belusca-Maito, Hermes *et al.* arXiv:1311.1113 [hep-ph]

[more](#)

.. of which self-citations: 0 records

Co-cited with: 604 records

- (4) [Measurements of Higgs boson production and couplings in diboson final states with the ATLAS detector at the LHC](#) - ATLAS Collaboration (Aad, Georges *et al.*) Phys.Lett. B726 (2013) 88-119 arXiv:1307.1427 [hep-ex] CERN-PH-EP-2013-103
- (4) [Combined coupling measurements of the Higgs-like boson with the ATLAS detector using up to 25 fb⁻¹ of proton-proton collision data](#) - ATLAS Collaboration ATLAS-CONF-2013-034, ATLAS-COM-CONF-2013-035
- (4) [Cyclotrons 1978 : Proceedings, Eighth International Conference on Cyclotrons and their Applications, Bloomington, Indiana, USA, September 18-21, 1978](#) - Hicks, J.W.
- (4) [Observation of a new particle in the search for the Standard Model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC](#) - ATLAS Collaboration (Aad, Georges *et al.*) Phys.Lett. B716 (2012) 1-29 arXiv:1207.7214 [hep-ex] CERN-PH-EP-2012-218
- (4) [Observation of a new boson at a mass of 125 GeV with the CMS experiment at the LHC](#) - CMS Collaboration (Chatrchyan, Serguei *et al.*) Phys.Lett. B716 (2012) 30-61 arXiv:1207.7235 [hep-ex] CMS-HIG-12-028, CERN-PH-EP-2012-220

[more](#)

Citation Log:
[show](#)

Figure 50. Citations for one of the Higgs Boson datasets

Cross-platform and external services

An example of INSPIRE's cross-platform/external services is the GitHub → Zenodo → INSPIRE integration, which enables software preservation and citation. Zenodo is a digital repository powered by Invenio that facilitates the sharing of research data and publications focusing on the long tail of research output, which generally means multidisciplinary or small datasets (or any other output) not hosted by a dedicated

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repository or service. Github is the standard platform for sharing software code and it is used by a large number of HEP scientists for that purpose.

The workflow in Figure 51 shows the way INSPIRE integrates code through Zenodo. Github provides an API that enables the connection to their service. Using it, Zenodo allows users both to authenticate using Github and provides a connector between the systems. When users connect both, every release of the software is automatically extracted by Zenodo. It keeps a tarball copy and assigns a DOI to it.

Figure 51. Same software in GitHub, Zenodo and INSPIRE

Zenodo's content is extracted by INSPIRE using the OAI-PMH standard. Both services agree on a set, which is described as a "community" by Zenodo, for software in High-Energy Physics. Once a day, INSPIRE harvests the community, and obtains any new record published by Zenodo.

INSPIRE creates individual records for each piece of software, keeping the DOI assigned by Zenodo, and creating a link to the original paper, which then appears in the corresponding author profile, along with any citations.

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As mentioned previously it is possible to receive a PID that was created by a third party, as it is the case here. It is not necessary for INSPIRE to mint another PID, since obtaining it from an external service is a very easy and straightforward process which can be replicated by any system that wishes to integrate the same material, because this workflow is generic enough to allow application by a wide variety of platforms.

This type of implementation, where the information spreads across platforms, and where each one of them is able to provide new value-added services, is based on shared and trusted identifiers. While the connection between Github and Zenodo is specific, the creation of a DOI allows the information to be correctly identified by any service.

4.4. Other on-going development

During the project, other initiatives to support the different communities have been developed. This section provides more information regarding the arXiv-INSPIRE integration, the role of RDF enabling services and other generic tools.

4.4.1. arXiv

The arXiv e-print repository is credited with transforming scientific communication in a number of disciplines by providing rapid, open and minimally-filtered access to pre- and post-print articles in physics, mathematics, computer-science and related fields. There will be over 90.000 new articles submitted to arXiv in 2014, and the collected corpus will soon exceed 1.000.000 articles. INSPIRE and arXiv complement each other and together form the primary information resource used by the HEP community.

PIDs for authors

Before the creation of ORCID, arXiv implemented a local author identifier scheme⁴². It provides user summary pages to encourage authors to claim and associate articles with their user accounts to avoid name ambiguity issues. Integration with ORCID is part of the 2014 arXiv roadmap⁴³:

⁴² http://arxiv.org/help/author_identifiers

⁴³ <https://confluence.cornell.edu/display/culpublic/2014+arXiv+Road+Map>

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"Add support for ORCID and other author identifiers associated with authors - We would like to support ORCID identifiers for better interoperability with other repositories implementing authority control and also as a route toward providing institutional statistics for member organizations (because ORCID is implementing storage of affiliation in the profile data)."

Cornell University Library

We gratefully acknowledge support from the Simons Foundation and supporters worldwide, including the CERN Library

arXiv.org

Search or Article-id (Help) Advanced search

All papers Go!

Simeon Warner's articles on arXiv

[1] [arXiv:1305.1476](#) [pdf, ps, other]
ResourceSync: Leveraging Sitemaps for Resource Synchronization
 Bernhard Haslhofer, Simeon Warner, Carl Lagoze, Martin Klein, Robert Sanderson, Michael L. Nelson, Herbert van de Sompel
 Comments: 3 pages, WWW 2013 developer track
 Subjects: Digital Libraries (cs.DL)

[2] [arXiv:1003.1345](#) [pdf, other]
Author Identifiers in Scholarly Repositories
 Simeon Warner (Cornell Information Science and Cornell University Library)
 Comments: 10 pages. Based on a presentation given at Open Repositories 2009
 Journal-ref: Journal of Digital Information, Vol 11, No 1 (2010)
 Subjects: Digital Libraries (cs.DL)

[3] [arXiv:0811.0573](#) [pdf]
A Web-Based Resource Model for eScience: Object Reuse & Exchange
 Carl Lagoze, Herbert Van de Sompel, Michael Nelson, Simeon Warner, Robert Sanderson, Pete Johnston
 Comments: 2008 Microsoft eScience Workshop, Indianapolis
 Subjects: Digital Libraries (cs.DL)

[4] [arXiv:0804.2273](#) [pdf]
Object Re-Use & Exchange: A Resource-Centric Approach
 Carl Lagoze, Herbert Van de Sompel, Michael L. Nelson, Simeon Warner, Robert Sanderson, Pete Johnston
 Subjects: Digital Libraries (cs.DL); Networking and Internet Architecture (cs.NI)

[5] [arXiv:cs/0702012](#) [pdf]
Plagiarism Detection in arXiv
 Daria Sorokina, Johannes Gehrke, Simeon Warner, Paul Ginsparg
 Comments: Sixth International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM'06), Dec 2006
 Subjects: Databases (cs.DB); Digital Libraries (cs.DL); Information Retrieval (cs.IR)

[6] [arXiv:cs/0610031](#) [pdf, ps, other]
Pathways: Augmenting interoperability across scholarly repositories
 Simeon Warner, Jeroen Bekaert, Carl Lagoze, Xiaoming Liu, Sandy Payette, Herbert Van de Sompel
 Comments: 18 pages. Accepted for International Journal on Digital Libraries special issue on Digital Libraries and eScience
 Subjects: Digital Libraries (cs.DL)

[7] [arXiv:cs/0609126](#) [pdf, ps, other]
E-prints and Journal Articles in Astronomy: a Productive Co-existence
 Edwin A. Henneken, Michael J. Kurtz, Simeon Warner, Paul Ginsparg, Guenther Eichhorn, Alberto Accomazzi, Carolyn S. Grant, Donna Thompson, Elizabeth Bohlen, Stephen S. Murray
 Comments: 8 pages, 4 figures, submitted to Learned Publishing
 Journal-ref: Learn.Publ.20.16-22,2007

Figure 52. arXiv's author pages

Implementation is underway and support will be deployed before the end of 2014. Where available, ORCID iDs will be added to the data exchange between arXiv and INSPIRE when users log-in to INSPIRE via arXiv. Such bi-directional exchange of ORCID iDs will minimize the burden on users and improve the utility of data from both services.

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PIDs for data

Limited support for data associated with articles is provided by arXiv in two ways. First, data may be uploaded with the article using arXiv's ancillary files mechanism⁴⁴. Second, during the period 2010 through 2013, arXiv operated a pilot to support remote data deposit in the Data Conservancy⁴⁵ for arXiv submissions⁴⁶. Now that the pilot has ended, arXiv will re-integrate data from the Data Conservancy using the ancillary files mechanism. In both cases, however, the implementation of data support is deficient.

Datasets in arXiv are not first class citizens; they are simply additional "files" that may be accessed via an article. They are not easily discoverable, and citation is supported only via the access URL. As described in this report, they need PIDs and appropriate metadata to support effective discovery, citation, and reuse. arXiv plans to assign DataCite DOIs for data stored using the ancillary files mechanism and also to add facilities to allow association of PIDs for data in other repositories with arXiv articles. Information about associated datasets, stored either locally or remotely, will be described for interoperating services using RDF.

4.4.2. RDF-based integrations

In parallel, **INSPIRE** has been preparing RDF support to handle arXiv's ancillary files and offer an open interface to its own database.

The current implementation provides a configurable module where different subsets of information can be exported. Figure 53 contains an example of configuration file to push works to ORCID.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<orcid-message xmlns="http://www.orcid.org/ns/orcid"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xsi:schemaLocation="https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ORCID/ORCID-Source/master/orcid-model/src/main/resources/orcid-message-1.1.xsd">
  <message-version>
    1.1
```

⁴⁴ http://arxiv.org/help/ancillary_files

⁴⁵ <http://dataconservancy.org/>

⁴⁶ http://arxiv.org/help/data_conservancy

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```

</message-version>
<orcid-profile>
  <orcid-activities>
    <orcid-works>
      {%- for record in records %}
        <orcid-work>
          <work-title>
            {%- for title in record.title %}
              <title>
                {{ title }}
              </title>
            {%- endfor %}
          </work-title>
          {%- for abs in record.abstract %}
            <short-description>
              {{ abs }}
            </short-description>
          {%- endfor %}
          Same for...
          <publication-date>, <work-type>,
          <work-external-identifiers>, <url>,
          <work-contributors>, <contributor>...
        </orcid-work>
      {%- endfor %}
    </orcid-works>
  </orcid-activities>
</orcid-profile>
</orcid-message>

```

Figure 53. Code snippet: BibRDF configuration file, ORCID work exporter

INSPIRE’s development is currently tackling the establishment of a SPARQL interface to support third-party services.

Dryad⁴⁷ does not routinely publish RDF. Instead, it attaches as much metadata as possible to their DOIs and lets DataCite handle the RDF interface. The RDF representation currently delivered by DataCite is limited, and does not provide available details such as the publisher, subject(s), references, copyright... Obtaining a complete

⁴⁷ <http://datadryad.org/>

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description of an object from Dryad may require the use of multiple endpoints (DataCite, CrossRef...).

Following their partner demands and use-cases, Dryad has approached DataCite about expanding their RDF as a solid alternative to the development of a RDF feed embedded in Dryad. This project is now part of DataCite’s agenda and its RDF support will be extended after its next metadata Schema version update.

4.4.3. Community support tools

Initially developed in ODIN year one, the ODIN Graph Visualisation Tool⁴⁸ links identifiers to provide a graphical view of the connections between creators and their research outputs, as seen in Figure 54.

Figure 54. ODIN graph visualisation tool

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/TomDemeranville/odin-graph>

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During the second year, further development work on the tool now provides ISNI interoperability, which enables seamless integration between ISNI and ORCID identifiers via common authors. The ImpactStory integration implemented at an ORCID codefest has been included as well in the codebase of the tool.

The tool was successfully demonstrated to relevant stakeholders, including the MRC NSHD, UKDA Dryad and ANDS.

Dryad and ANDS have both expressed interest in expanding and repurposing the tool to visualise their own datasets and ANDS have initiated a project to do so.

For other platforms and communities, once name identifiers have been implemented, this tool can be easily adopted, providing a full visualisation interface without internal development.

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Lessons learnt and future work

5. LESSONS LEARNT IN YEAR 2 BY ODIN AS A WHOLE

The results obtained from the proofs of concept provided extensive input in the design of concrete data management workflows, during the second year of the project. The workflows cover metadata gathering, persistent identifier assignment, publication and dissemination, but they have to be supported by stable and interoperable technical implementations. The case studies explored, MRC NHSC, ADS and INSPIRE show how such implementations are possible and allow the development of internal and third-party added-value services.

During the project, it became increasingly apparent that both disciplines could learn from each other much more than expected, and unforeseen commonalities arose. It is probable that the same approach(es) could be extended among other disciplines.

The commonalities and differences described in this document impact e-infrastructure providers directly. The inherent commonalities between research communities result in common workflows, where new developments can build to create adapted and specific solutions for their stakeholders. However, it is important to consider how a wider data landscape may require different approaches. For instance, institutional repositories and subject specific services should adapt their workflows to different constraints.

The fundamental areas requiring attention are:

- **Current and future needs:** new implementations and workflows should tackle real needs of the community and improve current practices. Internal constraints should be considered.
- **Technical implementation:** a well-planned implementation should make use of the available resources and build on successful and existing workflows, avoiding ad-hoc development. Starting small simplifies the transition.
- **Long term commitments:** although persistent IDs show their advantages very soon, all plans should consider the sustainability in the long term.
- **Community engagement:** successful implementations require a dissemination plan, helping the community to understand the advantages and usage of PIDs

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5.1. Challenges observed

Specific challenges have been encountered within each proof of concept, which need to be addressed to improve interoperability. However, most of them match both disciplines, namely: metadata quality, technical implementation and resources, community awareness and outreach.

The development of the case studies, as well as the potential new applications require the different disciplines to address their specific challenges following common strategies. A shared effort will reduce the gaps, allow new services and drive the different communities towards a successful open research.

5.1.1. Remaining challenges for HSS

There are reservations over information being ingested from ORCID back into the UK Data Archive, as there is insufficient capacity to check that the ORCID iDs that arrive represent accurate self-claims by authors. This is a general issue with trust and validation of third party metadata rather than an issue specific to ORCID. The issue is also more difficult to navigate for subject repositories than institutional repositories. The latter will have additional information on their researchers (in internal management systems for instance), which make it easier to validate claims.

The challenges met by author disambiguation via identifiers are clear (the problems demonstrated by Bohne-Lang and Lang[1]; Rotenburg and Kushmerick[10]; Taşkın and Al [11] to name but three), but the choice of which system to use, and the effort required in ensuring interoperability with all systems is not clear. The HSS proof of concept case studies would like to see greater take-up and awareness of name identifier across depositors – but this is a chicken and egg situation. Depositors will become more aware of the role of identifiers if they are encouraged or required to use them, but building the technical infrastructure to support identifiers within repositories also requires some impetus from the community.

In terms of object identifiers, there are two core issues to navigate. While the mandatory metadata is minimal, there are still cases within HSS where it is not available. This is particularly the case for publication year and creators, and there is a reluctance to provide a publishing date or creator where one is unknown. There is no technical

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solution to this issue, but further guidance from the DataCite metadata working group, and adaptation of community policies will help.

5.1.2. Remaining challenges for HEP

Given the particular characteristics of the community, big collaborations are the main data producers in High-Energy Physics. These collaborations are still developing their data publication practises and treat their research results in a heterogenic way. A supportive strategy is crucial to encourage re-use, provide adapted services and consolidate data publication among the community.

Currently, very few PIDs, in particular DOIs for data, are available in HEP. Basic metadata is not enough to describe correctly such datasets and make them findable and reusable, i.e. when demanding reproducibility of research results. Outreach actions and training are necessary to engage the researchers, obtaining both feedback to design description patterns and better metadata. Particular data citation actions are required to streamline and support the data citation approaches and enable citation tracking.

Regarding person identifiers, a small, but growing, fraction of the community has adopted ORCID during these two years. Person IDs are vital to avoid the complicated name disambiguation in a global community like HEP, as well as to support cross-platform services. A clear and transparent mapping between different identifiers would easy service compatibility and interoperability.

INSPIRE is already planning further integration, as well as the use of ORCID as an identity provider to foster the adoption in the community. In that regard, it is required to establish better data exchanges and validation with other platforms in the community, i.e. the publishers. That way it would be easier to compile trusted author and contributor profiles used in funding and career assessments.

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7. APPENDIX

7.1. Data Documentation Initiative metadata mappings

7.1.1. Mandatory DataCite schema 3.0 elements mapped to DDI 2.5

The table below maps the DDI 2.5 metadata currently used by the UK Data Archive.

DataCite	DDI 2.5 Fields ⁴⁹	DDI Description
1. Identifier	Holdings > callno OR Holdings > uri	Part of Holdings: <i>Information concerning either the physical or electronic holdings of the cited work. Attributes include: location--The physical location where a copy is held; callno--The call number for a work at the location specified; and URI--A URN or URL for accessing the electronic copy of the cited work</i>
2. Creator	AuthEnty	<i>The person, corporate body, or agency responsible for the work's substantive and intellectual content. Repeat the element for each author, and use "affiliation" attribute if available. Invert first and last name and use commas. Author of data collection (codeBook/stdyDscr/citation/rspStmt/AuthEnty) maps to Dublin Core Creator element. Inclusion of this element in codebook is recommended. The "author" in the Document Description should be the individual(s) or organization(s) directly responsible for the intellectual content of the DDI version, as distinct from the person(s) or organization(s) responsible for the intellectual content of the earlier paper or electronic edition from which the DDI edition may have been derived</i>

⁴⁹ <http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.5/>

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3. Title	titl	<i>Full authoritative title for the work at the appropriate level: marked-up document; marked-up document source; study; other material(s) related to study description; other material(s) related to study</i>
4. Publisher	accsPlac	<i>Location where the data collection is currently stored</i>
5. Publication Year	distDate	<i>Date that the work was made available for distribution / presentation. The ISO standard for dates (YYYY-MM-DD) is recommended for use with the "date" attribute</i>

7.1.2. Additional DDI 2.5 fields for DataCite to improve identifier interoperability

The table below maps additional fields from DataCite 3.0 and DDI 2.5 that can be used to aid interoperability. DDI 2.5 is the current version of DDI used by the UK Data Archive.

DataCite	DDI 2.5 field¹⁴	DDI Description
2. Creator	AuthEnty	<i>The person, corporate body, or agency responsible for the work's intellectual content</i>
*2.2 nameIdentifier	OthID	<i>Statements of responsibility not recorded in the title and statement of responsibility areas. Indicate here the persons or bodies connected with the work, or significant persons or bodies connected with previous editions and not already named in the description</i>
*2.2.1 nameIdentifier Scheme	N/A	

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7. Contributor	rspStmnt OR OthID	<i>Responsibility for the creation of the work at the appropriate level: marked-up document; marked-up document source; study; study description, other material; other material for study</i> OR <i>Statements of responsibility not recorded in the title and statement of responsibility areas. Indicate here the persons or bodies connected with the work, or significant persons or bodies connected with previous editions and not already named in the description</i>
7.1 contributorType	OthID > Type	
*7.3 nameIdentifier	OthID	<i>Statements of responsibility not recorded in the title and statement of responsibility areas. Indicate here the persons or bodies connected with the work, or significant persons or bodies connected with previous editions and not already named in the description</i>
*7.3.1 nameIdentifier Scheme	N/A	
*11. AlternateIdentifier	IDNo	<i>Unique string or number (producer's or archive's number). An "agency" attribute is supplied. Identification Number of data collection maps to Dublin Core Identifier element</i>
*12. RelatedIdentifier	OthrRefs OR relMat> ExtLink OR relPubl> ExtLink OR relStdy>	<i>Indicates other pertinent references. Can take the form of bibliographic citations</i> OR <i>Describes materials related to the study description, such as appendices, additional information on sampling found in other documents, etc. Can take the form of bibliographic citations. This element can</i>

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	ExtLink	<p><i>contain either PCDATA or a citation or both, and there can be multiple occurrences of both the citation and PCDATA within a single element. May consist of a single URI or a series of URIs comprising a series of citations/references to external materials which can be objects as a whole (journal articles) or parts of objects (chapters, appendices in articles or documents)</i></p> <p>OR</p> <p><i>Bibliographic and access information about articles and reports based on the data in this collection. Can take the form of bib. citations</i></p> <p>OR</p> <p><i>Information on the relationship of the current data collection to others (e.g., predecessors, successors, other waves or rounds) or to other editions of the same file. This would include the names of additional data collections generated from the same data collection vehicle plus other collections directed at the same general topic. Can take the form of bibliographic citations</i></p>
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7.1.3. DDI 3.2 Mapping to DataCite 3.0

Below are the DataCite mandatory metadata (required in order to obtain a DOI, bold) and other DataCite fields important for interoperability (*), with principal mappings to the DDI-Lifecycle model version 3.2⁵⁰. This is based on a fuller DDI 3.1 Mapping for DataCite metadata v2.2, which can be found on the DataCite schema documentation⁵¹.

⁵⁰ <http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.2/>

⁵¹ [doi:10.5438/0005](https://doi.org/10.5438/0005)

D3.3 Proofs of concept and commonality

WP3: Proofs of concept

Dissemination level: PU

Authors: Rachael Kotarski, Elizabeth Newbold (BL) - Stünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, Laura Rueda (CERN)

Version: 1_0 Final

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DataCite 3.0	Part of DDI elements	Contained by	DDI Description
*1. Identifier	Collection; DDIInstance; Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > InternationalIdentifier > IdentifierContent	<i>An identifier whose scope of uniqueness is broader than the local archive. Common forms of an international identifier are ISBN, ISSN, DOI or similar designator</i>
1.1. identifierType	Collection; DDIInstance; Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > InternationalIdentifier > ManagingAgency (*must be "DOI")	<i>The identification of the Agency which assigns and manages the identifier, i.e., ISBN, ISSN, DOI, etc. Supports the use of an external controlled vocabulary</i>
2. Creator	Collection; DDIInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Creator	<i>Holds the name of the creator and/or a reference to the creator as described within a DDI Organization scheme</i>
2.1 creatorName	Collection; DDIInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Creator > CreatorName	<i>Full name of the individual or organization. Language equivalents should be expressed within the International String structure</i>
*2.2. nameIdentifier	Collection; DDIInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Creator > CreatorReference > ID OR Individual > IndividualIdentification > ResearcherID > ResearcherIdentification	<i>ID of the object being referenced. This must conform to the allowed structure of the DDI Identifier and must be unique within the declared scope of uniqueness (Agency or Maintainable) OR Captures an individual's assigned researcher ID within a specified system</i>
*2.2.1. nameIdentifierScheme	Collection; DDIInstance; Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Creator > CreatorReference > Agency OR Individual > Individual >	<i>This is the registered agency code with optional sub-agencies separated by dots OR Brief description of the ID type. Supports the use of an external controlled vocabulary</i>

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			IndividualIdentification > ResearcherID>TypeOfID	
3. Title	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Title		<i>The title expressed using an International String to support multiple language versions of the same content</i>
4. Publisher	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Publisher > PublisherName		<i>Full name of the individual or organization. Language equivalents should be expressed within the International String structure</i>
5. Publication Year	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > PublicationDate > SimpleDate		<i>The date of publication</i>
7. Contributor	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Contributor > ContributorName		<i>Full name of the individual or organization. Language equivalents should be expressed within the International String structure</i>
*7.1. contributorType	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Contributor > ContributorRole		<i>A brief textual description or classification of the role of the contributor. Supports the use of an external controlled vocabulary</i>
*7.3. nameIdentifier	Collection; DDInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit	Citation > Contributor > ContributorReference > ID OR Individual > IndividualIdentification > ResearcherID > ResearcherIdentification		<i>ID of the object being referenced. This must conform to the allowed structure of the DDI Identifier and must be unique within the declared scope of uniqueness (Agency or Maintainable) OR Captures an individual's assigned researcher ID within a specified system</i>

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<p>*7.3.1. nameIdentifierScheme</p>	<p>Collection; DDIInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit</p>	<p>Citation > Contributor > ContributorReference > Agency OR Individual > ResearcherID > TypeOfID</p>	<p>This is the registered agency code with optional sub-agencies separated by dots OR Brief description of the ID type. Supports the use of an external controlled vocabulary</p>
<p>*11. AlternateIdentifier</p>	<p>Collection; DDIInstance Item; Origin; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage; StudyUnit Collection; Item Multiple relevant source elements</p>	<p>Citation > InternationalIdentifier (Collection or Item) > Call number (multiple relevant source fields) > UserID</p>	<p>An identifier whose scope of uniqueness is broader than the local archive. Common forms of an international identifier are ISBN, ISSN, DOI or similar designator The CallNumber expressed as an xs:string A user provided identifier that is locally unique within its specific type</p>
<p>*12. RelatedIdentifier</p>	<p>Archive; DataCollection; PhysicalDataProduct; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage ----- Multiple relevant source elements</p>	<p>OtherMaterial > ExternalURLReference OR OtherMaterial > ExternalURNReference ----- UserID</p>	<p>Contains a URL which indicates the location of the cited external resource OR Contains a URN which identifies the cited external resource ----- A user provided identifier that is locally unique within its specific type</p>
<p>*12.1 relatedIdentifierType</p>	<p>Archive; DataCollection; PhysicalDataProduct; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage Multiple relevant source elements</p>	<p>OtherMaterial > ExternalURLReference *relatedIdentifierType = URL OR OtherMaterial > ExternalURNReference *relatedIdentifierType = URN</p>	<p>UserID type must be one of: ARK, DOI, EAN13, EISSN, Handle, ISBN, ISSN, ISTC, LISSN, LSID, PMID, PURL, UPC, URL, URN</p>

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*12.2 relationType	Archive; DataCollection; PhysicalDataProduct; PhysicalInstance; ResourcePackage	OtherMaterial > Relationship	<i>Relationship specification between this item and the item to which it is related</i>
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